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Ph.D. Thesis

Frontier-based Exploration of Mobile-robot system using Bio-inspired Metaheuristic Optimization approaches

Graduate School of Yeungnam University

Department of Electrical Engineering

(Control and Electric Machinery, Power Conversion.)

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Advisor: Professor **Suk-Gyu Lee**

June 2020

Ph.D. Thesis

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Advisor: Professor **Suk-Gyu Lee**

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List of Abbreviations

CME	Coordinated Multi-robot Exploration
SRG	Sensor-based Random Graph
GWO	Grey Wolf Optimizer
MOGWO	Multi-Objective Grey Wolf Optimizer
ACO	Ant Optimization Colony
BA	Bat Optimization
WO	Whale Optimization
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization
ROS	Robot Operating System

Ph.D. Thesis

Frontier-based Exploration of Mobile-robot system using Bio-inspired Metaheuristic Optimization approaches

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Abstract

Mobile robot system consists of multiple problem-solving objectives in motion, particularly, path planning, localization, navigation, formation, target tracking, and exploration, in which a map is primarily required for a robot to solve its tasks, whereas exploration aims to produce one. For example, solving the path planning problem requires to set coordinates of start and goal robot positions in a known map and then, to compute a short available path among them. It means that in order to solve the path planning problem, a map should be given or exploration should be implemented in advance. This implies that autonomous exploration is a fundamental research issue in robotics that can be studied individually or paired with other objectives. Some examples of typical applications of the exploration operation are floor-cleaning, planetary exploration, underwater exploration, and other wide-known search and rescue exploration missions, which can be dangerous for humans in terms of emergency occurred situations. This study dedicates to the exploration problem of the mobile robot system.

The objective of exploration lies in constantly driving a robot in unknown areas without any initial parameters. While the robot moves to the uncertainties in the environment, the sensor information is gathered for creating a map. The finite constructed map in the end is the main aim of this mission. However, no less important role plays optimal time and trajectories of the exploration process, even though the mission is completed. For example, in case, a robot drives multiple times around an obstacle, it spends

much more total time and power consumption, which require to minimize by the computational methods. The selection of the computational algorithms depends on the several properties of the exploration such as map representation, robot vision, and the number of robots.

This thesis is proposed the novel methods in the exploration founded on an occupancy grid map and an occupancy probability map, sensory data, single and multi-robot systems properties. The proposed methods guide the exploration process heuristically, which leads the robot or group of robots to test the area by moving in random directions. In order to implement the stochastic exploration algorithm, the metaheuristic optimization algorithms were applied in this study.

The metaheuristic optimization (also called the nature-inspired optimization) is a bunch of algorithms, in which the animal behaviors are described into the mathematical models. The manner of the optimal solution guidance was imitated from the hunting, searching for food, or evolution processes in the animal nature. Some well-known optimization algorithms, just a few mentioned here, are based on wolf and whale hunting, searching for food by ants and bats, that were described in mathematic models called Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO), Whale Optimization (WO), Ant Optimization Colony (ACO) and Bat Optimization (BA) algorithms, respectively. This thesis applied the nature-inspired optimization techniques in the mobile-robot exploration for the effective searching of environment uncertainties.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Summary of mobile robotics

Robotics is a fascinating research field, for many reasons. It evolved from a computer into a wheeled, flying, or walking mechanical machine, which can collect information and interact or change the conditions in surroundings as well. Although it is obviously known what a robot is, it is hard to give a distinctive definition, which is the only characteristic of the robot. Checking the official definition in the Oxford English Dictionary, it says: “a robot is a machine capable of carrying out a complex series of actions automatically, especially one programmable by a computer.” It follows that the basic requirements of the robots are, first, carrying out actions automatically, and, second, programmable by a computer. Having said that a fundamental component of robots was not mentioned explicitly in the definition, which is the usage of sensors. Only sensors allow a robot to collect information about the environment and subsequently take any actions there.

It is known that there are various models of robots that are classified based on the environment applications in which they operate. Some of them can be given in this account such as conventional fixed manipulators [1], unmanned aerial robots [2], [3], underwater robots [4], humanoid robots [5], and wheeled mobile robots. Speaking of a mobile robot as a separate direction in robotics, it is

important to emphasize what makes this field distinguish apart from others. The main emphasis is that wheeled mobile robots operate purposefully in humans' environments in large- and small-scale terrains, in which humans usually move. Thus, the robot motion in indoor and outdoor space should be enough safe for others and independent that can be summarized in one term as autonomous navigation [6].

In mobile robotics, it is expected to move around and perform tasks in predictable and unpredictable difficult conditions. They need to deal with situations that are not precisely known in advance and that change over time. An example of mobile robots is a self-driving car, which should be a high-intellectual system for immediate reactions in events on a road [7], [8] that cannot be predictable in large terrains. The self-driving car is the application of the mobile robotics in outdoor space.

It is well-known and still used the type of mobile robot motion, which is called remotely controlled [9], [10]. This motion cannot be said autonomous, because it is controlled by an operator in a certain distance. This type of motion is often applied for dangerous and rescue missions. Fully autonomous mobile robots do not rely on an operator. But instead they make decisions on their own and perform tasks in uncertain terrains or in a constantly changing environment [11].

Despite the applications, the mobile-robotics has several problems in the autonomous navigation such as formation, path planning, localization, obstacle avoidance, and exploration. Each of the issue can be studied as a separate research. In this thesis, the contribution is in the exploration problem, which will be discussed further.

1.2 Problem Statement of Mobile-robot Exploration

For many years, people have used a geographical map to identify current locations and to move around the world by calculating distance according to the generally accepted standard. This agreement was established in the past by the observations of the sun and stars and corrected accurately the measurements after by chronometers including terrain features like lakes, mountains, and forests. In robotics, a map is highly necessary as well for itself localization and free driving without obstacle collisions. However, a robot needs a non-visual representation of a map, which is not like a human graphical map that has color and semantic notations of objects, because this information requires additional memory loads. Furthermore, the robotic system, especially mobile

robotics, is often applied in indoor environments, in which there does not have usually a digital map and where a piece of furniture can be moved wherever. Thus, this problem was formed and called the mobile-robot exploration.

In exploration, the main focus is uncertainties. A robot as a human has limitation in vision, which is related to sensors [12]. They have restrictions, which arise from several factors in what they can perceive. Furthermore, the range and resolution of a sensor is subject to physical limitations. They are subject to noise, which perturbs sensor measurements in unpredictable ways and hence limits the information that can be extracted. In addition, detecting a faulty sensor can be terribly difficult when they break. The second concern is related to actuation. The robot actuation involves motors that are, at least to some extent, unpredictable. Uncertainty arises from effects like control noise, wear-and-tear, and mechanical failure. Some actuators, such as industrial robot manipulators, are quite accurate and reliable. Others, like low-cost mobile robots, can be extremely flaky. Thirdly, uncertainties happen through algorithm approximations to usage real-time systems. This is related on the computational burdens. Many popular algorithms are approximate achieving timely responses through sacrificing accuracy.

Perhaps, a single robot can be represented as a point (x, y) in Cartesian plane as a simplest theoretical abstraction. The point (x, y) fully describes the state of the robot, which is called as a robot pose or robot position. Moving the robot involves changing the state from one pose to another ones. The robot operates on the plane, but not all of this domain is necessary available to the robot in the exploration task. The set of valid poses of the robot are known as its free space, explored space, or known area. If some states are not valid, then, it corresponds to obstacle or unknown place. This concept that the space can be free, occupied by obstacles or unknown formalizes the representation of environments. Given these definitions, the fundamental questions associated with the mobile-robot exploration can be asked: How can a robot determine priori which area is belong to obstacles, or known or unknown? How can a robot avoid repeated visits in known regions? These problems belong to robot sensing and robot mapping, which are together related to the mobile-robot exploration field [13], that stores continuously the robot poses and its sensing data perceived from environment in each driving step.

Up-to-now, there are many proposed algorithms for mobile robot exploration. These algorithms can be classified into deterministic and stochastic. Deterministic algorithms have proven to be reliable methods. With the task of investigating the unknown, they can completely cope. But there is one problem, that in the conditions of uncertainty, when there are sensory limitations and technical failures, described above, deterministic algorithms cannot solve the exploration problem by

uncompleted task or looping a robot in one place.

The stochastic algorithms are methods that use a random concept. This means that in real time, the robot explores an unknown area without any explicit logic of each robot step, but with certain reactions for crucial cases [14]. For example, if a robot collides with an obstacle or other robots, then the stochastic exploration algorithm has actions for this case. This thesis intends to propose the GWO, MOGWO, WO, and PSO exploration techniques applying them based on several properties of map representations and mobile-robot models (single- or multi-robot system). The original nature-inspired techniques were modified by the mobile-robotics platform and sensory received data.

It can be concluded that the mobile system has uncertainty complexity in the exploration task. The inaccurate sensing and mobility of a mobile robot can influence into computations in the autonomous navigation. Under such conditions, deterministic methods are not always reliable to use, even if their performance was proved successfully. Thus, the stochastic techniques are favorable for exploring uncertainties of environments.

1.3 Objectives of Mobile-robot Exploration

The overall goal of the exploration is to construct a finite map of the environment. However, achieving this goal requires to solve several sub-objectives, such as:

- Autonomous control motion. The mobile robot system should move independently without any remote control.
- Simultaneous upgrade a map by single or a group of robots in each robot step. It needs for algorithm computation and essential reaction on the events in real-time.
- Avoid collisions with obstacles and other robots. If a collision occurred, then this mobile-robot system can be considered as unsafe motion in environment.
- Fully constructing a map of an environment. The robot should reach all places of the environment.
- A robot should complete the mapping in certain time with finite map.

The exploration task is considered as completed and successful when the listed objectives are satisfied.

1.4 Contributions and outline of this thesis

This chapter presented some of the fundamental principles of autonomous mobile robotics. The definition of a robot was given in comparison with a computer. The distinguish features are its ability to perceive an environment and to navigate autonomously in the cluttered place relying on a certain computational algorithm. The brief summary of mobile-robot models introduced the different models of the mobile robotics, which can operate in separate environments such as ground, underwater, or air. Naturally, the motion on the ground differs from other conditions, that means that the wheeled robot has its own problems in the navigation.

The issues for a wheeled mobile robot can be listed as path planning, localization, formation, and exploration. The last one of the lists is studied in this thesis. The objectives of the exploration task can be summarized as the autonomous navigation to uncertainties avoiding obstacle collisions pursuing the goal of full coverage of the environment in limited time steps.

For the exploration of an environment, the following properties and functions should be considered: 1) single or multi-robot system can be used in this terrain, 2) topological or discrete representation is selected for a map, 3) obstacle avoidance function, 4) searching continuously the uncertainties preventing repeated visits in the same areas, 5) upgrading a map in each robot steps.

This study contributes to the strategies of autonomous exploration with respect to the sensor-based vision. In the beginning, the deterministic methods in this field was learned and evaluated their performances. It was found some drawbacks of this method, even when the performance is absolutely shows excellent results. Based on this, the novel stochastic algorithms were proposed based on single and multi-robot systems.

Figure 1.1 Brief summary of thesis content

Figure 1.1 demonstrates the big picture of this thesis with the guidance to the existing and proposed algorithms. There are seven chapters in the thesis, in which the introduction of mobile robotics, problem statement of the exploration is given in chapter 1 and the conclusion is summarized in chapter 7.

In chapter 2, it will discuss the related works of the deterministic approaches (Section 2.3) and the stochastic algorithms in Section 2.4. Also, the artificial intelligence methods in mobile robotics will be mentioned in Section 2.5. This topic will be discussed briefly, because it is out of this research study.

The original mathematical models of nature-inspired techniques will be explained in chapter 4. As far as, there are huge number of metaheuristic algorithms, it will be only considered the ones, which are applied in the explorations of this study. Thus, it can be listed the GWO, MOGWO, PSO, WO algorithms in this account.

In chapter 5, the modified exploration techniques based the bio-nature optimization techniques are introduced as the mathematical theories. However, the performances were tested by simulations in chapter 6 based on the exploration properties that were explained before in chapter 3.

Chapter 2

Survey on Preliminaries

2.1 Exploration Applications of Mobile Robot System

Mobile robots can be classified by the intended application field and the tasks they perform. In Figure 2.1, the classification of mobile robots is given in two groups: industrial and service. In two decades ago, the first mobile robot was applied in the industry conditions. It occurred so due to the well-defined environment that, as a result, simplified their design [15]. The industrial mobile robots are designed to support professionals, for instance, in the warehouse, and in weeding fields. Another robot model is a service mobile robot [16], [17] that assists humans at home like vacuum cleaners, in transportation like self-driving cars, in education, and in medicine, in defense applications such as reconnaissance, and in a more difficult environment as a Mars space [18]-[22].

Figure 2.1 Classification of robots by application field

This study does not have any limitations in the application of the mobile robot system. The exploration problem exists in the industrial and service spheres. For example, the wide famous application of the wheeled robot is a vacuum cleaner that requires constructing a map of the indoor rooms when it is launched for the first time. Customers without professional skills in robotics would prefer more the autonomous function of making a finite map rather than they will do it themselves by some software program tools [23]. The same reason of autonomous exploration application is required for workers in the industry. Thus, it can be said that the exploration is common task for houses and factories in the mobile robotics.

2.2 Algorithm Formalism

Algorithm is an executed program that can be run by an embedded computer for controlling the robot behavior. Figure 2.2 illustrates the general structure of autonomous mobile robot algorithm with input and output parameters. In this study, the proposed algorithms are layered into two stages: local obstacle avoidance module and global movement decision making. They, in both, are significant elements in the methodologies of mobile robotics. Excluding the obstacle avoidance module in the algorithm logic does not produce safe robot motion results using only a global controller. The input of the algorithm is sensory data and the output is the basic motor control of a robot.

Figure 2. 2 Two-layered taxonomy in the proposed exploration algorithms

Below, the two exploration directions are described in this chapter as the global movement decision making module. The decisions in the mapping process can be deterministic with explicit logic, or stochastic with random parameters [24].

2.3 Deterministic Exploration Approaches

2.3.1 Frontier-based exploration method

The frontier-based approach is pioneering algorithm in the sensory based exploration. It was firstly introduced by Yamauchi [25] for autonomous exploration. The methodology of the algorithm is based on the laser sensor data. While a robot moves, a sensor detects more new territory by increasing the boundaries, which are called frontiers, between explored area and uncertainties. The strategy of the frontier-based exploration consists of two parts: a) detection of frontiers, and b) driving to nearest frontier.

The frontier-based approach was applied in many studies in the past and up to today [26] - [28]. Also, it is often used in conjunction with others for more advanced solutions in the mobile robot exploration [29], [30].

A. Frontier Detection

The frontier-based exploration algorithm is applied in an occupancy probability grid map. It means that a map is represented as a grid with certain probability values of each cell. The probabilities of unknown, open, and occupied cells are given by the following:

$$\begin{cases} \text{unknown cell} = 0.5 \\ \text{open cell} < 0.5 \\ \text{occupied cell} > 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

It assumes that the frontier line is edge-explored cells, which adjoin to unexplored cells. In figure 2.3, it illustrates the frontier line in the occupancy grid map.

Figure 2.3 Frontier detection in occupancy grid map: a) occupancy grid map, b) frontier cells, c) inserted sensor rays with 180-degree sweep in the occupancy probability map in MATLAB

B. Navigation to Nearest Frontiers

As it was observed in Figure 2.3 that the frontier line is some number of adjacent cells to uncertainties. In the frontier-based exploration algorithm, a robot attempts to navigate the nearest

frontier cell according to its current position. For that, the depth-first search concept is used for finding the shortest obstacle-free path to the frontier cell. In some cases, if a robot is unable to reach the frontier cell after a certain amount of time, then, it relies on the frontier cell is not accessible and another new frontier cell should be reselected.

It can be noted that the frontier-based exploration algorithm is applied for a single mobile robot and the Coordinated Multi-robot Exploration method is its extension for multi-robot system in.

2.3.2 Coordinated Multi Robot Exploration method

The Coordinated Multi-robot Exploration (CME) method was introduced by Burgard [31], [32]. The CME proposed the cost and utility concepts for selecting short distance to frontiers and for efficiently task assignments among other robots in an occupancy probability map.

The CME was applied in many studies of mobile robotics, which enhanced or modified the CME algorithm. The novel approach and new cost function for the CME were proposed in [33] and [34], respectively. Senarathne and Wang [35] aimed for a balanced distribution of robots to explore unstructured environments. They applied two approaches for the exploration. The first one is the original CME and the other one is the proposed approach for the repositioning of robots over the environment. Puig et al. [36] had a similar purpose as our study, but they only applied the deterministic global optimization for CME. The exploration was improved by K-Mean clustering that gives each robot different assignments to travel separate places (K regions) simultaneously at the same speed. The approach resulted in the lowest variance of regional waiting time and the lowest variance of average waiting time of all regions consumed by the motion of multi-agents during the exploration process. The similar clustering principal was applied in CME as well using the Voronoi-space partitioning algorithm [37] and Map Segmentation concept [38].

Further, the cost and utilities calculations are described considering the multi-robot system.

A. Cost

The cost computes the distance needed to reach the frontier cell for each robot. The sensor view in terms of occupancy grid map covers several cells around a robot (Figure 2.4, a and b). For these

cells, the cost is computed using occupancy probability, Euclidean distance, and the sensor observation (equation 2.2). If the cell has been explored before, then the cost of this cell in the previous step is appended to the cost of the new position (Figure 2.4, c). Otherwise, if the ray beams open the cell at first time, then the cell is denoted as a frontier cell without the backward costs of the previous steps (equation 2.3).

$$V_{x,y} = \min \{V_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y} + \sqrt{\Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2} \cdot P(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y})\} \quad (2.2)$$

$$V_{x,y} = \min \{\sqrt{\Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2} \cdot P(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y})\} \quad (2.3)$$

where $\Delta x, \Delta y \in \{-1, 0, 1\} \wedge P(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y}) \in [0, occ_{max}]$

The occupancy probability value $P(occ_{x,y})$ of the unknown cell is 0.500, whereas the cell occupied by an obstacle has a value close to 1, and a value close to 0 represents the certainty that the cell is open and obstacle-free. Depending on the probability that the sensor covers the cells at certain distance, the occupancy values decline whenever the sensors touch the cell.

Figure 2.4 Representation of sensor observation in the occupancy grid map: a) the sensor touches eight neighbor cells, b) the neighbor cells have the name V1, V2, V3, V4, V5, V6, V7, V8, V9 and cost, c) the costs V6, V7, V8 do not have the intersecting sensor observations

The aim of the cost function in the CME algorithm is to find the minimal value among the cell neighbors, which is the optimal next position of a robot.

B. Utility

For a single mobile robot system, the search of minimal cost can be enough to determine the position. However, the multi-robot system requires the collective-organization interaction during the exploration. The CME approach introduced the utility for the arrangement of the tasks between robots.

The essence of the maximizing the utility is that initially each cell of the whole map had identical values. While the robots search, the utilities of their frontier cells decreases (equation 2.4). The robots have less interest to visit the cells with low utilities. This is the reason why the robots try to search for new areas, which they have not yet explored to maximize utility values.

$$U_i^c = U_{i-1}^c - P (\|occ_{x,y}^c - occ_{x,y}^r\|) \quad (2.4)$$

The cell utility U_i^c equals the state of the previous modifications U_{i-1}^c , which can be changed by itself or other robots before, and the probability occupancy of the selected cell subtracting the current robot position. The utility U_i^c is opted as the maximum value by (equation 2.5) in the iteration i .

$$(i, c) = \max\{U_i^c - V_{x,y}\} \quad (2.5)$$

The CME algorithm computes cost and utility in real-time in each iteration time.

2.3.3 Sensor-based Random Graph method

The Sensor-based Random Graph (SRG) algorithm [39], [40] is an exploration approach, which builds a roadmap in the form of a graph or tree with an associate safe region detected by the robot sensor (Figure 2.5). The SRG is an evolution of the Sensor-based Random Tree algorithm (SRT) defined in [41].

Figure 2.5 Roadmap of SRG exploration algorithm

In real time when robots drive, the graph of environment is constructed by using a randomized local planner that automatically realizes a tradeoff between information gain and navigation cost. Each node of the graph is free collision path that has been traveled by at least one robot. In this method, the exploration is directed through the selection of free boundaries from a given position to continue the exploration. Once the robot is located in an area where it is not possible to continue with the examination, the robot is automatically sent to the parent node of the current position to find new unexplored areas.

The SRG and SRT are fundamental methods in graph-based exploration branch. Up to now, the methods are widely used as improved [42], or modified [43] algorithms. For example, Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (RRT) [44], Random Exploration Graph (SRG) [45] are variations of SRT. In study [46], the tree sampling function was proposed for the modified RRT algorithm for decreasing the computational memory resources.

2.4 Stochastic Exploration Approaches

In the recent decade, researchers had imitated the numerous numbers of optimization models of various animals in metaheuristics. They gained knowledge of the distinctive behaviors of animals that is peculiar to some species, in which a swarm uses the knowledge and experience obtained through evolutions, physical rules, searches of food, or emitted sounds. It was found that, for example, the ants have certain behavior while they search a food. They lay down the pheromone trails in order for the other ants to find the food easily after them without randomly walking for a search. Thus, Dorigo et al. [47] proposed the Ant Colony Optimization algorithm based on the

swarm ant manner of searching for food. Another some well-known methods are the genetic algorithm (GA) [48], particle swarm optimization (PSO) [49], grey wolf optimizer (GWO) [50] and whale optimization (WO) algorithms [51].

The number of agents classifies the metaheuristic algorithms into single-solution-based and population-based algorithms. In both classes, the solutions are improved over the course of iterations with one single agent or an entire swarm of agents, respectively. The main advantage of population-based approaches is their ability to avoid stagnation in the local optima due to the number of agents. The swarm can explore search space more and faster than a single agent. Regardless of this, the benefit of one class over the other depends on its application in a certain problem. However, it is important to mention the No-Free-Lunch (NFL) theorem for optimization, which assures that there is no algorithm with universal optimal solution by all criteria and in all domains [52].

These swarm optimization techniques are widely used in various fields with their applications: economic load dispatch problem [53], characterizing wind speeds [54], and many other applications that can be listed for this account [55]-[57]. Bellow, some studies are discussed related to the mobile robotics field using metaheuristic algorithms.

2.4.1 Nature-Inspired Optimization Methods in Mobile Robotics

Recently, novel metaheuristic algorithms find their applications in the mobile robotics. It was found that the techniques were applied mainly in path planning [58]-[62], formation control [63], [64], and in exploration problems as well. Considering the mobile-robot exploration, the metaheuristic algorithms creates new branch of methodologies that can be taken the advantage of optimization of existed algorithms or the development of a new approach. In Table 2.1, the latest major studies are summarized based on the metaheuristic algorithms in the mobile-robot exploration.

Table 2.1 The nature-inspired approaches in the mobile-robot exploration

Approaches	Description	Optimization	Exploration
Fang et al. [65]	Adjusted velocity and coarse direction parameters for the optimal solution	Numerical optimization	Social potential field, multi-robot system
Wang et al. [66]	Applied two stages: exploration and	A star, PSO	Frontier-based, multi-

	walking. Robots explore frontier points in local sub-regions (exploration). Then, they can move other regions navigated by PSO (walking).		robot system
Fuzzy adaptive FORDPSO method [67]	Analysis and comparison of the influence of coefficients fractional order RDPSO and fuzzy adaptive FORDPSO in the exploration problem	Fuzzy adaptive FORDPSO	Reward and punishment mechanism as nature selection concept for swarm, multi-robot system
CBDF and NIA method [68]	Applied directional and exploring based movements. Robot explores in the direction provided by CBDF and search short ways to reach up in the area using NIA	PSO, BFO, BA	CBDF, multi-robot system
Adaptive robotic bat algorithm (ARBA) method [69]	Applied the adaptive inertial weight strategy and the Doppler effect for improving obstacle avoidance and repeated exploration works	BA, Doppler effect	Sensor-based, target selection method, multi-robot system
On-line path planner [70]	Applied artificial pheromone for avoiding redundant exploration and time waste. During the search, the planner follows the waypoints. The Fuzzy controller allows the robots to move to the target.	Artificial pheromone, Fuzzy controller	Sensor-based, target selection, multi-robot system

Fang et al. [65] applied the behavior-based method called social potential fields to obtain the course direction and move the robots toward unexplored areas. Then, they optimized the system by fine-tuning the angle and speed of each robot. The simulation showed that the most optimal coverage of unknown space by the multi-robot system with robot speed from 0.7 to 1.0 m/s and angle in the range -0.2 to 0.2 rad. This type of deterministic optimization has minimal effect compared to the present trends and does not take into account the other requirements of the robot system.

Wang, Y. et al. [66] applied the frontier-based method, A star and PSO in two stages. In the exploration stage, the method discovers available frontier points around each robot in its own subarea and selects the shortest distance using A star algorithm. In the walking stage, each robot is

navigated through subareas according to the latest exploration information and the robot positions using PSO algorithm. It means that PSO is applied for the task assignment in the clustered area, like in the previously mentioned study [36].

PSO algorithm is widely used in mobile control systems because of its concept of upgrading the position and velocity of a swarm. Wang et al. [67] proposed and explored modified PSO algorithms such as Darwinian PSO (DPSO), robotic DPSO (RDPSO), fractional order RDPSO (FORDPSO), and fuzzy adaptive FORDPSO. The last two were proposed to adjust control coefficients, especially in multi-robot exploration problem.

The combined Clustering Based Distribution Factor (CBDF) and nature-inspired algorithm (NIA) method [68] is a hybrid approach to probe unknown areas. It is divided into the direction- and exploration-based movements. Each robot is assigned a direction by the CBDF to a specific subarea. For the exploration, three NIAs such as PSO, bacteria foraging optimization (BFO), and bat algorithm (BA), are compared to determine their efficiency.

In study [69], the BA algorithm was improved for multi-robot target searching and was named adaptive robotic bat algorithm (ARBA). This modified ARBA algorithm allows safely building path to a target avoiding the obstacle collision problem. A similar target selection concept was performed in [70]. The artificial pheromone and fuzzy controllers help the multi-robot systems to navigate efficiently by distributing the search between robots and avoiding repeated visits in explored regions.

2.5 Neural Network Methods in Mobile Robotics

Another approach branch in exploration that is completely different in theory and practice is neural network. Usage of Reinforcement Learning (RL) and convolutional neural network (CNN) in the mobile exploration are such attempts, which have been proposed in studies [71–73]. The exploration-based approach on neural networks differs considerably from the frontier-based approach in terms of environment, perception and control system. Visual sensors (cameras) scan a place for further computation using image-processing algorithms [74]. The output of the calculation is the interaction of the robot with the environment. Lei Tai et al. [75] conducted a survey of leading studies in mobile robotics using deep learning from perception to control systems. One more survey from Zou et al. [76] have presented the review of neural networks and its applications for mobile robotics as well.

In study [77], the neural network was trained for safe obstacle collision avoidance. It uses two

feedforward neural networks based on function approximation with a backpropagation learning algorithm. Two different data sets are used for training the networks and reducing environment noise. The output result of the neural network navigation is increasing robot speed.

The study [78] proposed two processes in the exploration problem: 1) the recognition of physical structures such as elevators, stairs, doors based on camera images and supervised learning, 2) identification of the proximity of obstacles by laser sensor. The experiment proved that Deep Learning [79] can be applied for exploration problem using two processes from camera and laser sensor. However, the correct learning of the network is required for detection objects in the indoor environment.

The two neural networks were implemented in study [80] for determining free space using ultrasound range finder data and for finding a safe direction for the next robot section. The similar study in navigation of a mobile robot was proposed in study [81], in which the neural network was trained online with extended backpropagation for motion controlling and potential fields algorithm for obstacle avoidance. A novel path planning method based on convolutional neural network (CNN) was proposed in research [82] in binary occupancy map. The implementation of CNN was explained in details in the paper.

In general, it can be said that CNN [83] and Deep Reinforcement Learning [84], [85] are widely used for mapping navigation in the mobile robotics, even though there are many types of neural networks. Also, it should not be excluded that the neural networks can be applied along with the metaheuristic algorithms. For example, the Whale Optimization algorithm (WO) trained the multilayer perceptron neural network replacing the backpropagation algorithm [86]. The result showed better results of 20 test functions in terms of accuracy and convergence.

In the robotics community, the neural network and its enhanced Deep Learning models were accepted as a powerful tool and begun to use them. However, the demanding challenges in robotic control and robotic perception cannot be solved only by the neural network concept, because a robot requires real-time reactions in uncertainty conditions around it. Also, the techniques are quite costly for the computational process. The limits and potentials of deep learning in robotics were discussed at large in paper [87].

Chapter 3

Mobile Robot Exploration Properties

3.1 Motivation

Before diving into the proposed algorithm methodologies and simulations, it is worthwhile describing some properties of the exploration systems. In the related works of the chapter 2, it was mentioned a variety of environment applications that can be applied a mobile robot. Relying on the circumstances, a particular robot model or communication type can be selected for mapping the environment. This chapter provides the introduction of the exploration properties. The choice of map representations, robot and sensor models, communication types and simulation tools, is rich that should be selected in order to achieve exploration mission efficiently.

In the robotics algorithms, robot motion is changed according to the received sensor data. Although, it does not occur so implicitly. If a sensor sends ranges, in which it will mean that an obstacle is close located, a robot is required to move twice as fast by the left wheel for avoiding it by right side. In the real world, robots have to drive at certain distances and points in their workspace that demand to set the mathematics of mobile robot motion. The wheeled robot model and its motion kinematics are studied in this chapter by the reason that the kinematics properties effect on robot driving and algorithm logic.

As it was mentioned about the strong connection between perception and motion, the classification and types of sensors are discussed in Section 3.3. It introduces the sensor models with their benefits and drawbacks in some conditions. Despite that the sensor characteristics such as accuracy, range, and resolution are given for understanding the receiving data for further usage them in the mapping.

When a robot can sense an environment and set appropriate motion, then, it is relatively easy to build a map. The term of map can take the analogy “storage”, in which stores information about obstacle positions, robot position and trajectories, and/or exploring areas. In Section 3.4, the map representation is discussed in its classification. In the exploration, the map model plays important role for mobile robot systems.

In Section 3.5 and Section 3.6, the mobile robot systems and their communication models are presented. The number of agents in the mobile robot system can influent into the optimization process usefully, however, the communication model should be considered inside of robot group and between a multi-robot system and a map as well.

The simulation and experiment tools for robotics are presented in Section 3.7 and Section 3.8, respectively.

3.2 Wheeled Robot Model

In order to implement the mobile robotics application, it is important to consider the physical kinematics models of a wheeled robot, because this affects the primary motion control tasks of posture regulation [88]. In contrary with other robot models as a drone or humanoid, the wheeled robot has more stable balance due to the fact that wheel robots always are in touch with ground at all time. Consequently, three or two wheels are sufficient to guarantee stable balance for mobile robot system.

In Figure 3.1, it shows four major wheel models such as fixed standard wheel, castor wheel, Swedish wheel, and ball wheel [89]. As it can be seen, they differ widely in their models, and therefore the choice of wheel type can have a large effect on the robot motion. The standard wheel and the castor wheel have a directional motion due to their primary axis of rotation. It means that these wheel types steer along a vertical y-axis while they move in various directions. The small distinction between these wheels is that the standard wheel can carry out the steering motion with

no side effects, whereas the castor wheel rotates around an offset axis, causing a force to be affected to the robot chassis during steering. The Swedish and ball wheels are designed so that they are less constrained by directionality than the previous two others. The small rollers of Swedish wheel attached around the circumference of the wheel are passive and the wheel's primary axis serves as the only actively powered joint. The ball wheel is a truly omnidirectional and it may be actively powered to spin along any direction.

Figure 3.1 The four basic wheel type: a) standard wheel, b) castor wheel, c) Swedish wheel with 45 degrees angle, d) ball wheel

In this study, two motorized standard wheels and not-motorized ball are selected to use for indoor environment application (Figure 3.2). It was considered the wheel geometry peculiar to these wheel types, which is called the differential drive [90]. The differential drive is when a robot has two wheels that are driven by two independent motors, and a non-motorized ball wheel, which follows these two others and applied for stability and support. The advantages of differential drive are a simple model that has two motors for steering and it allows the robot turn easily in place. The disadvantages are that it requires a third point of contact (a ball wheel) and it cannot drive laterally without turning. But the differential drive is the most famous configuration and applied for a car or tank. Figure 3.2 shows the two-wheeled differential robot model, based on which further presentations of algorithms will be proposed.

Figure 3.2 Differential-drive mobile robot with two standard wheels and one ball wheel

3.3 Robot Kinematics

In mobile robotics, it is needed to be able express mathematically the mechanical behavior of robot motion in order to build a robot and to program software. When a robot moves in its workspace, the range of possible poses can be computed in advance based on its motion kinematics. Despite that paths and trajectories can be precomputed as well. During the last two decades, the robotics community has achieved a complete understanding of the mobile robot kinematics and even its dynamics (force and mass of a robot) [91], [92].

One of the features of the mobile robot kinematics is that there is no any onboard device on the robot for estimation its position instantaneously. Yes, odometry sensor is able to provide a robot position according to initial zero values, but it has issue with wheel's slippage detection. Thus, it can be summarized that there is no direct way to measure a mobile robot's position over time, therefore, the precise description of mobile robot kinematics should be investigated according to all possible motion errors (constraints) and environment features like floor smoothness, room size, and dynamic obstacles.

The process of understanding the kinematics of a wheeled robot begin with the process of describing the representation of robot position and, then, the motion of wheels.

3.3.1 Robot pose

To describe robot motion in a map, it needs to consider a map coordinate system, which is called in some literatures the global reference frame $\{X, Y\}$ and a robot position is denoted as the local reference frame $\{X_r, Y_r, \theta_r\}$. Such division into global and local frames of references is particularly important in mobile robotics because of its self-contained and mobile nature. It gives a chance to compare accordance of previous and current positions and to map the robot driving in process. In Figure 3.3, it illustrates the relation of the global and local references frames. The equation 3.1 and 3.2 can calculated the selected point location according to the current robot position by following:

$$X_g = X_r + \cos(\theta_r) \quad (3.1)$$

$$Y_g = Y_r + \sin(\theta_r) \quad (3.2)$$

where θ_r is orientation of a robot, which rotates in 360 degrees of angle.

A next position in certain selected distance L in meters can be described as:

$$X_g = X_r + \cos(\theta_r) \cdot L \quad (3.3)$$

$$Y_g = Y_r + \sin(\theta_r) \cdot L \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.3 The global reference frame and the robot reference frame with an arbitrary angle deviation between the reference frames

Throughout this analysis it assumes that the robot model as a rigid body on wheels, operating on

a horizontal plane. The total dimensionality of this robot on the plane is three (3D), two for a position in the plane (2D) and one for orientation along the vertical axis, which is orthogonal to the plane.

3.3.2 Forward kinematic model

In this study, the differential drive motion was selected with two motorized standard wheels and one not-motorized simple ball wheel. Supposed the wheel diameter is d , the center point between two wheels is P , which is located in equal distance l from P . The spinning speed of each wheels is given as ω_1 and ω_2 . Consequently, the forward kinematic model would predict the robot's overall speed in the global reference frame:

$$X_g = \begin{bmatrix} X_r \\ Y_r \\ \theta_r \end{bmatrix} = f(l, d, \theta_r, \omega_1, \omega_2) \quad (3.5)$$

The motions of each wheel can be combined to compute the motion of the robot as a whole.

3.4 Perception

In human world, it is obvious fact that the eye vision is required to us for learning information around. The same as for a mobile robot, it is not safe to set only relative power of the motors for moving in certain distance. A robot can meet a static or dynamic obstacle on the route that is better to drive far in certain distances. For example, solving the obstacle avoidance problem demands to adjust the distance limitation how close a robot can be near a wall. It can be noted that the vision needs not only for exploration problem, but for all mobile robot problems as well.

In robotics, a sensor is a component that measures some aspects of environment. The onboard laptop in the robot uses these sensor data to control the robot motion. The most famous sensors in robotics in the distance sensor that can measure distance between a robot and object by infrared light, ultrasound or laser. More semantic information about the environment can be obtained by analyzing images taken by a camera. Even the cheapest camera can provide large amount of data from images, which is a significant advantage in perception. But the image processing of the

pictures takes heavy computing resources.

Sensors are classified into two classes: proprioceptive and exteroceptive. A proprioceptive sensor measures inertial states of a robot for example a speedometer. An exteroceptive sensor measures external states to the robot such as a distance to objects. In this study, the main focus belongs to the exteroceptive sensors (ultrasounds, infrared light, optical sensor, triangulating sensor, laser scanner), which will be discussed below [11].

Distance sensors usually transmit a signal and then receive its reflection (if any) from an object. The distance is computed by time that elapses between sending a signal and receiving it:

$$s = \frac{1}{2} v \cdot t \quad (3.6)$$

where s is the distance, v is the velocity of the signal and t is the elapsed time. One-half is taken because signal travels the distance twice: to the object and then reflected back.

Figure 3.4 Distance sensors: a) ultrasound sensor, b) infrared light sensor, c) optical distance sensor, d) laser scanner sensor

3.4.1 Ultrasound distance sensor

Ultrasound has the frequency about 20.000 hertz that is good for sensing at night and in water. The advantage of this sensor is that it is not sensitive to changes in the color or light reflectivity of objects, nor to the light intensity in the environment. However, an ultrasound sensor is sensitive to texture: fabric will absorb some of the sound, while wood or metal will reflect almost all the sound. Also, ultrasound is cheap compared with other sensors and widely used in indoor and outdoor environments. There are large amount of studies using the ultrasound sensors in the exploration of

environment, just a few are mentioned here [93] – [95]. The main disadvantage in the short distance measurement and the absence of focus for measuring a specific object.

3.4.2 Infrared proximity sensor

Infrared light is light whose wavelength is longer than red light. It has wavelengths between 700 to 1000 nm. The sensor uses simple light to detect the presence of an object by measuring the intensity of the reflected light. The measurement is not very accurate because the reflected intensity also depends on the object reflectivity. This is the reason why this sensor is called proximity sensor. The study [96] used six infrared sensors for the multi-robot exploration that is declared itself as the most low-cost robot application.

3.4.3 Laser scanner

Usually ultrasound and infrared sensors are placed around the robot in order to detect objects in 360 degrees. Even through, the angle to the object cannot be measured accurately. With a laser sensor, the width of the beam is so small that a large number of lasers would be needed to detect objects at any angles. A full rotation of 360 degrees enables a laser scanner to generate a profile of the objects in the environment. The figure 3.5 illustrates the map that is constructed by the laser scanner.

Figure 3.5 A map of indoor environment obtained by a laser scanner

The laser scanner is the most popular and effective sensors in the mobile robotics [97]-[99]. In this thesis, the exploration is implemented only by the laser scanner sensor.

3.4.4 Sensor characteristics: range, resolution, accuracy

The last subsection in the sensor topic should belong to the reading of sensing data parameters, because it is important to set them correctly for mapping. The sensor measurement can be characterized by its range, accuracy, resolution.

The range is the length of the set of values that can be measured by distance sensor. As it was discussed before, the laser scanner beams focus mostly power into a narrow beam, therefore, it has the larger range than others.

The resolution refers to the smallest change that can be measured. Some sensors can give the same distances in centimeters or in millimeters. In digital computer world, it means that the same distance will be represented in 100 or 1000 elements in array. It is important parameter in the mapping as well.

Accuracy refers to the closeness of a measurement to the real-world quantity being measured. For example, if an object is located in 2 meters far in real world, but the value is different in a map, then, the sensor values are not accurate.

3.5 Map Representations

To efficiently navigate in an indoor, a robot should have essential information about the place. The received sensory-data must be collected and integrated in one representation, which is a map, for further decision-making process. Conventionally, a map representation can be classified into metric and topological maps. In metric maps, the positions of some objects, mainly the obstacles and robot position, are stored in a common reference frame. Within topological maps, this information is stored in relative positions [100]. In Figure 3.6, it depicts the real map and the comparison between metric and topological map representations. It can be seen that the positions of A and B objects are expressed in the x- and y-axes in the coordinate system. In contrary, the

topological map is stored the objects with their spatial relations by sampling the distance between them.

Figure 3. 6 Representation of distinction between metric and topological maps

Over and above, the metric maps have two subcategories: discrete maps (also called grid maps) and continuous maps [11]. The same object in two maps is stored in different lists of coordinates. In Figure 3.7, a, the object consists of the cells: (2,3), (2,4), (2,5), (3,4), (3,5), (4,5). The same object in the continuous map of Figure 3.7, b is stored only the coordinates of boundary positions: (2,3), (2,6), (5,6).

Figure 3. 7 a) A district map with the occupied object; b) continuous map of the same object

It can be seen that the object in the district map does not accurately repeat the shape of the triangle. However, it depends on the grid resolution that is a scalar value in cells per meter. It is possible to adjust the resolution by decreasing the size of cells for representing objects more accurately. It should be noted that, in this case, the memory load will be raised in parallel with map accuracy. In continuous maps, it is some difficulties as well in increasing memory size when there are a large number of objects or the shape of objects is not as primitive as a simple triangle, which has only three vertices.

It is worthy to say that the metric discrete maps (grid maps) are commonly used to represent a map of indoor environments in mobile robotics, as it will be shown in the simulations of Chapter 7.

3.5.1 Inside of a Grid map

A human geographic map can illustrate multiple objects as roads, buildings, lakes, mountains, etc., and their properties as colors, shapes, symbols, and texts. A map in robotics has limitations in representing a certain number of object types. Conventionally, it displays obstacles mostly, free space (also called configuration space), unknown space, and a robot.

In a grid map, each cell has coordinates and a value as a weight, which determines type of object

that occupied this cell. The weights of various objects should have distinctive values for encoding them, as an obstacle, for example.

The simplest encoding for cells can be encrypted as a value of 1 indicates an obstacle and a value of 0 indicates empty free cell. Figure 3.8, a illustrates the cell contents of the grid map of Figure 3.7, a. This method of representing a map by 1 and 0 values is called as a binary occupancy map.

Figure 3.8 Grid maps: a) Binary occupancy map with binary values, b) Probabilistic occupancy map with probabilistic values

However, sensors on a robot are not enough accurate to determine only occupied or free cells in certain distance. It occurs because a ray of a laser sensor has an unequal signal power alongside the ray beam. Therefore, it makes sense to assign a probability to each cell indicating how certain the object is in that cell. The numbers on the cells, which are over and around the obstacles in Figure 3.8, b, are the occupancy probabilities. It can be observed that the occupancy probabilities of the triangle obstacle range from 0.5 to 1 value.

Aside from the obstacle occupancy, the probability can be applied for representing unvisited (unknown) cells, and not-occupied visited (open) cells. In mobile-robot exploration, while a robot drives, it upgrades cell status from unknown to known. The mission of the exploration is to visit all unknown cells. In order to classify which cell is explored, the weights for unknown and open cell are given above in equation 2.1.

3.6 Single and Multi-robot Systems in Exploration

Some complex tasks require multi-robot system in factories, agriculture companies and in other large organizations. The advantage of using multi-robot system is fast execution and assignment of different tasks to each robot. The design of teamwork in the mobile robotics is called collaboration or coordinated multi-robot system.

In exploration, a single mobile robot and multi-robot systems are often used in studies. Depends on a problem formulation, one of the systems can be highly required for specific exploration objectives. Some examples of exploration tasks that require the multi-robot system rather than a single robot:

- the search and rescue mission in large indoor and outdoor environment
- underwater or space tasks where a human cannot easily access

To sum up, it can be noted that a group of robots can perform a fast completion of an exploration tasks or some others due to the collaboration in acting one objective. However, a fundamental question for the multi-robot system is how multiple robots communicate between each other.

3.7 Centralized and Decentralized Communication in Exploration

Pursuing a goal to build a multi-robot system, it needs to consider a point of how a team of robots update a map together and how they communicate in a group. There are two main techniques in the exploration for designing of multi-robot system: centralized and decentralized systems.

The centralized exploration is when all robots have one common map. They sense the environment simultaneously that allows them to know about the progress of each other. Each robot sends sensor data and coordinates to a central computer, and after, it assigns tasks individually based on general computation analysis. The centralized system is that it is relatively simple to implement, but the main drawback is that such a system is easy to destroy if one robot is broken. Also, the centralized system is difficult to extend because adding more robots adds execution loads to the central computer.

The decentralized (distributed) exploration is the individual map building. Every single robot of the multi-robot system has its own map of exploration progress. The coordination of sharing data is needed only if robot locations intersect. Compared to the centralized system, the decentralized

system is more robust. Losing one robot reduces the performance, but does not destroy the whole system. Also, it is easy to adopt a new agent in the decentralized multi-robot system.

In this study, the centralized strategy is applied, which computes the cost of travelling distance locally for each one in real time and the utility values, which all robots upgrade through iterations.

3.8 Simulation tool: Robotics System Toolbox in MATLAB

Coming from the methodologies to practical field, it should be some platform for simulating a robot, testing algorithms and implementing experiments in real-world constrains. The process of creating a robot software from zero without any libraries is quite complex tasks that requires to solve many primitive issues of the visualization, physical models of a human world and etc. It is common when researches use some robotics libraries for focusing on high-level problem solving.

In recent years, the option of commercial and open source robotics platforms is dramatically increased, that positive effects in the development of robust, easy-to-use, accurate software tools for the simulation of robotic models, sensors, and control in virtual environments. The surveys [101] and [102] listed the platforms such as Player/Stage Project [103], USARSim (Unified System for Automation and Robotics Simulation) [104], SimRobot [105], ROS (Robot Operating System) [106], MATLAB with Simulink and Robotics System Toolbox [107], and etc.

In this study, Robotics System Toolbox of MATLAB platform is applied. The toolbox enables to create an indoor environment, simulate a sensor models, and using some basic robotics algorithms. In Table 3.1, the list of functions of the toolbox, which was applied for the simulations of Chapter 7.

Table 3.1 The list of Robotics System Toolbox functions applied in this study

map = binaryOccupancyMap (width, height, resolution)	creates a 2-D binary occupancy grid with a <i>width</i> and <i>height</i> of 10 m. The default grid resolution is one cell per meter
map = occupancyMap (width, height, resolution)	creates a 2-D occupancy map object representing a world space of <i>width</i> and <i>height</i> in meters. The default grid resolution is 1 cell per meter.

checkOccupancy (map, xy)	returns an array of occupancy values at the <i>xy</i> locations. Each row is a separate <i>xy</i> location in the grid. Occupancy values can be obstacle free (0), occupied (1), or unknown (-1).
getOccupancy (map, xy)	returns an array of occupancy values at the <i>xy</i> locations in the world frame
insertRay (map, pose, scan, maxrange)	inserts one or more lidar scan sensor observations in the occupancy grid <i>map</i> using the input lidarScan object <i>scan</i> to get ray endpoints. End point locations are updated with an occupied value. If the ranges are above <i>maxrange</i> , the ray endpoints are considered free space. All other points along the ray are treated as obstacle-free.
[endpoints,midpoints] = raycast (map, pose, range, angle)	returns cell indices of the specified <i>map</i> for all cells traversed by a ray originating from the specified <i>pose</i> at the specified <i>angle</i> and <i>range</i> values. <i>endpoints</i> contains all indices touched by the end of the ray, with all other points included in <i>midpoints</i> .
rayIntersection (map, pose, angles, maxrange)	returns intersection points of rays and occupied cells in the specified <i>map</i> . Rays emanate from the specified <i>pose</i> and <i>angles</i> . Intersection points are returned in the world coordinate frame. If there is no intersection up to the specified <i>maxrange</i> , [NaN NaN] is returned.
setOccupancy (map, xy, occval)	assigns occupancy values, <i>occval</i> , to the input array of world coordinates, <i>xy</i> in the occupancy grid, <i>map</i> . Each row of the array, <i>xy</i> , is a point in the world and is represented as an [x y] coordinate pair. <i>occval</i> is either a scalar or a single column array of the same length as <i>xy</i> . An occupied location is represented as true (1), and a free location is represented as false (0).
show (map)	displays the binary occupancy grid <i>map</i> in the current

	axes, with the axes labels representing the world coordinates.
--	--

3.9 Experiment tool: MATLAB and ROS Integration

Aside from that Robotics System Toolbox enables design and simulate the mobile robot system, it provides to make experiments in the real-world constraints. The toolbox has the integration tool between MATLAB and Robot Operating System (ROS), which allows achieving the connection between the two platforms [108], [109].

Robot Operating System is open-source robotics-based platform with the collection of software for robot system development. In this study, the ROS-interface is used for communication with a TurtleBot robot [110], [111]. It allows to acquire sensor data and send control commands to the robot. The computation and analysis of the sensor data are operated in MATLAB part following some algorithm logic. The communication bridge between these two platforms carries through the Robotics System Toolbox.

3.10 Conclusions

When a problem and objective are formalized considering environment circumstances, then a developer can adjust parameters for solving mapping efficiency. In this chapter, the exploration properties were introduced and selected for further proposed searching techniques. The robot kinematics and perception models were presented as major topics in the mobile robotics. The wheeled mobile robot has the most stable kinematics model comparing to drone or humanoid robots, which is continuously in contact with the ground surface. In this study, the two standard wheels and ball wheel were chosen for the mobile robot. However, the differential drive by these three wheels have the constraints (every wheel has own ones) and slippage can be occurred in some cases. Considering the advantages and disadvantages of standard wheels and ball wheel, they were selected among others for indoor exploration.

As the sensor classification shows that the selection is depends on what needs to measure: distance, attitude, or velocity. In mobile robotics, the distance sensors are widely applied that are

differ in ranges, resolutions, accuracies, applications in environments, and prices. Any sensor connected with a computer returns discrete values within fixed range, which can construct a map of previous and current states.

Robotic motion in the environment requires having a map for a robot. A map stores the robot positions of previous and current iterations. It can be said that a map represents the states of the robot and obstacles that were experienced before. The map representation can be either in grid cells or in graph. In the exploration of this thesis, a grid map is applied, which consists of known, unknown, and occupied cells that are saved in certain discrete values.

The techniques how the mobile robot system is designed determine the method of how a map is upgraded. The multi-robot system is able to have centralized and decentralized communication between agents and a map. In this study, the centralized communication was used for multi-robot and single robot systems due to its convergent storage in one map model.

Except theoretical properties in the exploration, there were introduced the simulation and experiment tools in robotics. In this thesis, the MATLAB with Robotics System Toolbox and ROS were selected as simulation platform for demonstration the proposed techniques for exploration applications.

Chapter 4

Reactive Behavior in Exploration

4.1 Motivation

The reactive robot behaviors are those that solving small tasks in order to complete global mission of the system. In this study, for example, the obstacle avoidance is a basic task for the exploration mission, which should be solved as well. It means that the reactive behavior is reactions on certain events that cannot be ignored in the more complex system. It occurs when the action is related only to the occurrence of an event and does not depend on data stored in memory of onboard computer.

The reactive solutions are presented as algorithms. The most famous ones are line following an object, obstacle avoidance, and turning an obstacle. In this study, the reactive algorithms are pure pursuit (can be called as path following), obstacle avoidance, and multi-step path planning algorithms, which are applied in the exploration. This chapter limits to present only these three reactive behavior approaches, because they are parts of the complex exploration behavior that will be explained in the Chapter 6.

At first, the complex behavior of the mobile robot exploration arises from the simple algorithm

as the pure pursuit of global waypoints in Section 4.2. This algorithm can compute an angular velocity in order to reach a certain global waypoint based on a current robot location and its linear velocity. Then, Section 4.3 introduces the obstacle avoidance methodologies for the exploration. It explains the reaction on detecting an obstacle. In this study, a selection of safe local waypoints is proposed. Section 4.4 shows the multi-step path planning for efficiently motion in the explored areas.

4.2 Pure Pursuit algorithm in Exploration

In the proposed techniques of exploration, the concept of local and global waypoint selection is used for obstacle avoidance and global planner, respectively. The Pure Pursuit algorithm is able to calculate the curvature path, linear velocity, and angular velocity for a robot using its location and selected waypoint. In general, this approach is tracking algorithm for following a certain point [112]. The Pure Pursuit algorithm is old and famous approach that was applied in many studies before [113] – [115].

The Pure Pursuit algorithm was developed as a controller in the Robotics System Toolbox of MATLAB platform. The controller is able to calculate robot's linear and angular velocities, to sample a curvature path into some waypoints, and additionally to smooth robot trajectories [116].

Figure 4.1 Pure Pursuit controller in MATLAB: a) sampling the path into six points, b) smoothing the robot driving trajectory

In Figure 4.1, it represents the sampling and smoothing the robot's trajectories by Pure Pursuit

controller. The number of sampling points is counted automatically according to the long or short distances to the global waypoint. The deviation of smoothing path is computed based on the lookahead parameter, which is given in the settings. In case, the lookahead parameter is greater than it showed in Figure 4.1, b, then, the actual path will curve less.

4.3 Obstacle avoidance approach in Exploration

An autonomous mobile robot must be capable to drive free in obstacle-cluttered environment avoiding any collisions. In order to move safely to a goal position, a safe path should be constructed for a robot in offline or in real-time. If a position of obstacle is known, then, a free path can be easily calculated offline in free configuration space. When it is uncertain, then, a robot should decide and precompute a path in real-time as it gradually explores the environment by a sensor.

It assumes that a robot can detect obstacles. There is one issue, which is how to avoid an obstacle. It is commonly known two techniques for obstacle avoidance:

- A straightforward wall following algorithm
- Right/Left obstacle following algorithm based on a goal direction

In this study, right-wall-following algorithm was applied when an obstacle is already detected. The method how to detect them in right time and distance is proposed using local waypoints.

4.3.1 Local Waypoints for Obstacle Avoidance

Obstacles exist in all environments, which the robot should pass safely through. However, the detection range of robot vision d has a distance limitation for planning the obstacle avoidance ahead. It needs some safe scenario for obstacle avoidance in d area ($d > V_{dist}$). Thus, V_j is applied for changing the current robot direction to $g(i)$ waypoint. Equations (4.1) and (4.2) calculate the option of local waypoints on the x- and y-axes, respectively:

$$V\{n\}_{x,j} = x_{robot} + \cos(\theta_{robot} + \theta_{V\{n\}}) \cdot L \quad (4.1)$$

$$V\{n\}_{y,j} = y_{robot} + \sin(\theta_{robot} + \theta_{V\{n\}}) \cdot L \quad (4.2)$$

where a robot is surrounded with n local points ($n = 5$) at a distance L in meters in front of the robot. $\theta_{V\{n\}}$ is the angle between $V\{n\}$ with respect to the x-axis. The values x_{robot} , y_{robot} , and θ_{robot} belong to the current robot position in j th iteration. θ_{robot} changes dynamically from 0 to 360 degrees.

Figure 4.2 Local waypoint representation: a) robot position and its five local points in distance L and angles $\theta_{V\{n\}}$; b) Additional ray beams in $V\{n\}$ for monitoring obstacles in intervals; c) Local waypoints face with the obstacle in the simulation.

Figure 4.2 illustrates the representation of local waypoint positions around the robot at a certain distance and angles. Since the local waypoints are dots in one pixel-size, there are additional checks in $V\{n\}$ in eight directions for monitoring obstacles between them in $V_{dist}/2$ range (Figure 4.2, b). Thus, an obstacle can be detected on time with high probabilities. Figure 4.2, c shows the local points in the simulation. In this case, points V_1 , V_2 , V_3 cannot be selected because their locations and additional bounced rays bring the information about finding obstacles. The next local point will be randomly taken between V_4 and V_5 .

It has to be noted that when $V\{n\}$ is selected finally, a robot should have several j th time steps to reach this point, and then, it can obtain a new task $g(i + 1)$ where to drive.

4.4 Multi-step Path planning

Supposed that the obstacle avoidance problem is solved. There is still one topic, which is essential to solve in the exploration. It is high-level navigation, that can be called as path planning, multistep path planning, or task scheduling in the exploration.

The path planning in the exploration can be applied as:

- a method for scheduling the order of unexplored places. For example, a robot begins to construct a map of an unknown indoor environment. It needs task scheduling which region should be explored at first.
- a method for selecting a short path to new area. After a robot explored one place (one room in an office), it should find a short path to the next unexplored place.

Nowadays, the path planning can be solved by the conventional deterministic approaches (A* algorithm, Dijkstra's algorithm) or by the novel stochastic approaches (PSO path planning, Ant colony path planning, and other bio-inspired algorithms). In this study, the nature inspired techniques are solved the path planning, that are presented in Chapter 7. Here, the switching strategy of local to global waypoint is introduced.

4.4.1 Global Waypoints for Exploring Uncertainties

When the exploration process begins, a robot goes straight without any assigned $g(i)$ point. The initial driving direction is not significant because the entire space is not known. Once the robot reaches an obstacle, the first global waypoint will be generated.

The computation of $g(i)$ point relies on frontier points. Every $f(k)$ has its position f_p and cost f_c that are updated and stored in the stack each iteration. The cost is estimated by the Euclidean metrics according to the current robot position in (4.3).

$$f_c(k) = \sqrt{(x_{f_p(k)} - x_{robot})^2 + (y_{f_p(k)} - y_{robot})^2} \quad (4.3)$$

where x_{f_p} and y_{f_p} are values of the k th frontier point position along the x -axis and y -axis, respectively.

Meanwhile, some f points should be removed, which are no longer frontiers according to the

conditions:

- Exclude an f point if it touches an obstacle
- Exclude an f point of the previous step if it is already explored
- Exclude an f if its f_c to the robot position is less than the length of the sensor rays ($f_c < d$)

Figure 4.3 shows the illustration of frontier points in the simulation. The red circles in Figure 4.3, a denote the frontier points of current and previous j th iterations located in the stack. Several bounced rays from the obstacle can be seen in Figure 4.3, b, which are not inserted in the stack of frontier points. This shows that the frontier line lies on the open regions of uncertainties.

Figure 4.3 The frontier point representation at iteration j : a) the red circles are stored at the frontier points after the filtering; b) the robot position in the simulation

It can be concluded that the stack of f points change dynamically by inserting and deleting operations. The f_p and f_c values of the frontier line are modified in accordance with robot driving. The array of frontier points is another input parameter for generating the $g(i)$ point, which can be found using the bio-inspired optimization algorithm.

4.4.2 Waypoint Dynamics

The switching behavior among local and global waypoints is presented in Figure 4.4. Here, the transition occurs on two conditions. If a sensor returns a ray range smaller than the constant V_{dist}

value, then, the local waypoint mechanism should be activated. When the distance G_{dist} between x_{robot} , y_{robot} and g point is less than the constant value of the maximum ray length d , the next global waypoint should be found.

Figure 4. 4 Flowchart of the waypoint switching strategies

4.5 Conclusion

A robot exhibits reactive behavior when its actions depend only the current values returned by its sensor. In this chapter, the reactive behavior algorithms were presented as supplemental ones for more complex task. The exploration mission demands driving forward the uncertainties, where unpredictable events can occur, which some actions should be considered. There are many simple algorithms known that could be described in this chapter. However, only some were presented for the exploration problem, because there no any other cases occurred in the searching application.

Thus, the pure pursuit algorithm was introduced for calculating the robot linear and angular velocities. The local waypoint concept was proposed for the obstacle avoidance, which were selected in the safe explored areas in distance less than maximum sensor range. In the multi-step path planning, the global waypoint concept was presented as a selection a waypoint in the uncertain

areas. Here, it illustrated the meaning of frontier points, their cost calculation, and the principal of adding and excluding them in the frontier point array. The frontier points are upgraded their positions and costs in each short interval called the iteration. The Section 4.4 will be investigated more in Chapter 6.

In the end, the switching strategy were presented between local and global waypoints by the reason that a robot is not able to do several reactive behavior actions simultaneously. If the robot faces with obstacle, it cannot continue to drive the current global waypoint. Otherwise, when there is no obstacle, the robot keeps the direction only to the global waypoint. The conditions when the reactive behaviors should be run, was given in the subsection 4.4.2.

It is worthy to emphasis that the principal of robot driving in the global waypoint was explained in this chapter, although how to calculate a global waypoint will be introduced in the Chapter 6. It needs to say that the frontier point array is input data for the bio-inspired optimization algorithms.

Chapter 5

Metaheuristic Nature-Inspired Optimization Approaches

5.1 Motivation

Robotics is an interdisciplinary science that combines mechanical and computer science for designing a robot system under a certain task. Mostly cases, the tasks are required high-degree of autonomy in how a robot can interact with its environment. However, a physical surrounding can have a full of uncertainties that a robot should handle it autonomously. For example, a robot is designed to find an object by given images in unknown place with dynamic and static obstacles.

To overcome the complex tasks, optimization techniques have been proposed for solving some issues by finding the best solution or dismissing some options. Somehow, to simplify a decision-making process in mobile robotics.

The metaheuristic techniques are generally known as the nature-inspired optimization algorithms, can be presented as novel optimization approach in the mobile robotics. Metaheuristic strategy guides the agents to progressively improve the overall solution. The solution is iteratively checking across some random elements that extends the possibility options. Meta-heuristics may not yield an absolute best solution unlike deterministic methods. But quite often they produce sufficiently good solution in most cases within a reasonable amount of time [117].

In this study, the metaheuristic techniques were applied in the mobile-robot exploration problem for optimization the navigation in uncertainties. There are many algorithms are known in the metaheuristics, however, the most famous was used in this research such as PSO, GWO, MOGWO, and WO algorithms.

5.2 Mathematical Models

5.2.1 Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm

PSO algorithm is a stochastic optimization method that mimics the social behavior of bird or fish swarms [49]. An individual of the swarm is denoted as a particle, which is a point in the coordinate system. Each particle has a current position x_i and a velocity V_i . During the search of a solution, new points can be found by adding V_i to x_i . The velocity allows the swarm to move by a certain manner saving the neighborhood and swarm intelligence among all particles, which are denoted as the personal best and global best solutions. In every j th iteration, a new particle x_i is evaluated by the objective function, which gives the cost solution. The cost can be compared with the previous personal best solution and global best solution. If the new cost of x_i is better than the previous one, then the particle is stored as the personal best solution P_i . If this personal solution is better than all personal solutions of other particles, then the particle is stored as the global best solution P_g .

In equation 5.1, the PSO algorithm updates a particle velocity at iteration j based on the personal best and global best solutions.

$$V_i^{j+1} = w \cdot V_i^j + c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (P_i - x_i^j) + c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (P_g - x_i^j) \quad (5.1)$$

where w is an inertia weight, which decreases from 1 to 0 during a search, r_1 and r_2 are

random numbers uniformly distributed in the range $[0, 1]$, and c_1 and c_2 are acceleration weights.

In equation 5.2, the next particle position is found through the previous point position and the velocity. Then, the objective function will evaluate the cost of x_i^{j+1} .

$$x_i^{j+1} = x_i^j + V_i^{j+1} \quad (5.2)$$

In case the cost does not enhance the previous cost, then it will not update the personal and global particle solutions.

In summary, the particle swarm in the PSO algorithm is guided by the global best solutions P_g , which can be changed when a personal best of a particle surpasses P_g . The velocity allows the swarm to move in the search space divergently or convergently depending on the stochastic parameter and weights.

5.2.2 Grey Wolf Optimizer algorithm

GWO is a population-based metaheuristic algorithm, which mimics the wolf hunting process. Population- and single-based optimization algorithms differ from each other in the number of agents used to carry out a search of a global optimum. Each agent is a candidate for finding a global optimum. Figure 5.1 shows the GWO simulation. The search begins when all agents obtain random x, y values, where $\text{lower bound} \leq x, y \leq \text{upper bound}$. Then, the cost function defines the best candidates α, β, γ from among them in each iteration (Figure 5.1, a). Every single agent needs to compute $D_\alpha, D_\beta, D_\gamma$, and then, X_1, X_2, X_3 can be computed. The parameters A and C are upgraded in each iteration. The same calculation will be repeated in each run time for every search agent.

(a)

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \quad (5.3)$$

(b)

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{D}_\alpha &= |\vec{C}_1 \cdot \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{X}|, \\ \vec{D}_\beta &= |\vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{X}|, \\ \vec{D}_\gamma &= |\vec{C}_3 \cdot \vec{X}_\gamma - \vec{X}|, \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{X}_1 &= \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 \cdot (\vec{D}_\alpha), \\ \vec{X}_2 &= \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 \cdot (\vec{D}_\beta), \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

$$\vec{X}_3 = \vec{X}_\gamma - \vec{A}_3 \cdot (\vec{D}_\gamma),$$

(c)

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \frac{\vec{X}_1 + \vec{X}_2 + \vec{X}_3}{3} \quad (5.6)$$

Figure 5.1 GWO simulation at first iteration: a) initialization of grey wolf population and search the dominated agents by the cost sphere function of equation 5.3; b) calculate the divergence of each agent positions to α, β, γ agents in equation 5.4; and c) calculate the next agent position by equation 5.5 and

5.6. The position of agent $x(t) = 2.3531, y(t) = 2.8036$ will change the position in next iteration to $x(t+1) = 0.2914, y(t) = 0.9727$, where $t = 1$

It is worth noting the meaning of the random and adaptive parameters A and C for GWO. The two phases make the transition between the divergence (exploration) and convergence (exploitation) in the optimal solution search by the GWO parameters, which are calculated as follows:

$$A = 2a \cdot r_1 - a \quad (5.7)$$

$$C = 2 \cdot r_2 \quad (5.8)$$

where the value of a decreases linearly from 2 to 0 using the update equation for iteration t :

$$a_t = a_t - \frac{a_0}{t} \quad (5.9)$$

and r_1 and r_2 are random values ranging from 0 to 1.

It can be observed that the GWO finds $\vec{X}(t+1)$ based on the average value of the non-dominated agents. The priority is defined from among the three best agents and other wolves. However, there is no hierarchy coefficient which emphasizes alpha as the best solution and beta and gamma as the second and third best solutions, respectively. In previous studies [118-120], the hierarchy coefficients that provide the weights for non-dominated solutions were presented. Also, the nature-inspired algorithms have significant applications in different fields. Due to this, they have attracted the attention of scholars [121] – [123].

5.2.3 Whale Optimization algorithm

WO is a population-based metaheuristic algorithm [51] that mimics the foraging behavior of humpback whales. The WO algorithm presents three mathematical models: encircling prey, spiral bubble-net attacking mechanism, and searching for prey.

The encircling prey operator assumes that the best whale position is close to the global solution, based on which the others update their positions $\vec{X}(t+1)$ in the best whale neighborhood as follows:

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}^*(t) - \vec{X}(t)| \quad (5.10)$$

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \vec{X}^*(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D} \quad (5.11)$$

where \vec{X}^* is the position of the best whale at iteration t and the vectors A and C are stochastic coefficients, which are calculated in the same way as in the GWO approach using (5.7) and (5.8).

The hunting begins with the searching for prey operator ($A > 1$), in which a whale swarm follows a randomly selected whale \vec{X}_{rand} at iteration t . In equation 5.12, the vector D computes the distance of the current whale \vec{X} to the random whale position. Here, the stochastic parameter \vec{C} gives some additional deviations for \vec{D} that allows finding the $\vec{X}(t+1)$ position around the \vec{X}_{rand} solution (5.13).

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_{rand} - \vec{X}| \quad (5.12)$$

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \vec{X}_{rand} - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D} \quad (5.13)$$

when $A < 1$, the WO algorithm applies the spiral bubble-net attacking operator. In this strategy, the whales update their positions using two methods with 50% probability of selecting one of them. The first is a shrinking method, in which a swarm pursues a selected best whale position \vec{X}^* by (5.10) and (5.11). The second is a spiral-shaped method, which mimics the helix-shaped movement of humpback whales. A whale swarm updates the next position using the vector \vec{D} , which is literally the distance between \vec{X} and \vec{X}^* whales without a stochastic parameter (5.14), (5.15).

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{X}^*(t) - \vec{X}(t)| \quad (5.14)$$

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \vec{D} \cdot e^{b \cdot l} \cdot \cos(2\pi l) + \vec{X}^* \quad (5.15)$$

where b is a constant number that determines the shape of the logarithmic spiral and l is a random number in the range of $[-1, 1]$.

Switching between these two methods, the shrinking and spiral-shaped, the parameter p , which is a random number in the range $[0, 1]$, is given. When $p < 0.5$, the swarm moves based on the shrinking mechanism (5.11). In the case where $p \geq 0.5$, the spiral-shaped method is activated for updating positions (5.15).

To sum up, the swarm in WO can be guided by the best or random solutions depending on the value of vector A . The spiral bubble-net attacking strategy has two approaches, which can be called depending on the p value. In both methods, the swarm follows only the best whale solutions. At the end of the search, the parameter \vec{a} decreases to zero, which results in the convergence of the search place of whale swarm solutions completely.

5.3 Multi-Objective Grey Wolf Optimizer algorithm

Two new components were integrated into MOGWO for performing multi-objective optimization: an archive of the best non-dominated solutions and a leader selection strategy of alpha, beta, and gamma solutions [124], [125]. The archive is needed for storing non-dominated Pareto solutions through the course of iterations. The archive controller has dominant sorting rules for entering new solutions and for archive states. The size of the archive is closely related to the number of objective functions, which is named segments or hypercubes. Figure 5.2 (a) shows the archive of three hypercubes with the non-dominated solutions for the t -iteration.

The second component is a leader selection, which chooses the least crowded hypercube of the search space and offers available non-dominated solutions from the archive (Figure 5.2, b). In case there are only two solutions, the third one can be taken from the second least crowded hypercube.

Figure 5.2 Two modules of MOGWO: (a) the archive, which consists of three hypercubes, and (b) the leader selection mechanism

Generally, it can be said that the archive stores the best solutions for each objective function. It saves them not only as alpha, beta, and gamma agents, but also with the segment priorities, which are defined by the number of total solutions. Thus, the global best solution can be chosen among the local ones in the archive. This selection mechanism in MOGWO prevents the picking of the same leaders. In other words, it avoids stagnation in local optimal points. Figure 5.3 shows the full algorithm of MOGWO.

Figure 5.3 MOGWO algorithm

5.4 Conclusion

In this Chapter 5, the mathematical models of the nature-inspired techniques were presented, particularly the PSO, GWO, MOGWO, and WO algorithms. Each algorithm mimics certain swarm species and take the analog of hunting or searching for food operations. The PSO algorithm simulates the social behavior of bird or fish swarms. It proposed the concept of agent velocities and their costs, which are upgraded based on the best agent solution. The GWO algorithm is a prototype of grey wolf hunting strategy. The optimization process is guiding by the hierarchy of best three solutions. The WO algorithm mimics the whale bubble-net hunting strategy, which has two methods: shrinking and spiral methods. They are switched with 50% probability of selecting one of them. The MOGWO is the multi-objective GWO algorithm, which presented multi-objective concept. It was illustrated the archive of the objective solutions and the hypercube of clustering the best solutions. In the original papers of the PSO, GWO, WO, and MOGWO metaheuristic algorithms, the comparisons are demonstrated between them.

This chapter introduced the original nature-inspired algorithms. In the Chapter 6, the modifications will be presented based on the exploration task of multi-robot system and single robot system. The mathematical models will be given and explained.

Chapter 6

The Proposed Hybrid and Modified Algorithms of the Nature-Inspired Optimization Techniques in Mobile-robot Exploration

6.1 Motivation

In robotics, exploration pertains to the process of scanning and mapping out an environment to produce a map, which can be used by a robot or group of robots for further work. Based on the type of environment, exploration can be one of the following: outdoor, indoor, or underwater, using a mobile-robot or multi-robot systems. In this chapter, the exploration is focused on indoor environment by single robot or multi-robot system, which are equipped with ranging sensors. It can be assumed that these robots with onboard sensors can scan an environment without any difficulties by walking randomly around. However, their motion is not efficient, which can result in an incomplete map coverage. As a solution to this issue, this study proposes an algorithm that enhances the efficiency of the multi-robot exploration by using the nature-inspired optimization strategies.

In this thesis, the problem is formulated as the exploration of an unknown space by robot motion with laser sensor. However, some studies are known that focus only on research concerning static

sensor coverage errors and robot motion in unknown environments [126], [127]. In the case where the sensors are mobile, the two terms coincide in meaning and scope. In other words, both studies have the common task to build a finite map.

In this chapter, the GWO exploration is introduced for single and multi-robot systems in the binary and probabilistic occupancy map representations. The MOGWO exploration algorithm as a multi-objective exploration system. The PSO and WO exploration algorithms for the single mobile robot systems are presented as well.

6.2 GWO exploration algorithm Based on Multi-robot System

Here, we optimize the process of constructing a map by a group of mobile robots. As the optimization technique, the GWO metaheuristic algorithm was used with modification on the task of sensor coverage. It generates random parameters for the maximum positions that change the order. Thus, the hierarchical optimizer reforms the robot position selection, which is the deterministic exploration approach. In cases where the optimization is not possible in real-time processes, a stochastic technique in the absence of a priori information about the environment is performed as one of the profound solutions of area coverage for the mobile sensor system.

Table 6.1 describes the proposed hybrid exploration. Initially, space is unknown with the utility equal to 1. The eight cells V_c , where V_c is $V1_{x,y}$, $V2_{x,y}$, ..., $V8_{x,y}$, around a robot are the candidates for the next position. The deterministic technique computes the cost and subtracts the utilities from the cost for the eight cells. Then, the metaheuristic optimizer defines three maximum utility values that are assigned as alpha, beta, and delta candidates with priorities in the listed order (line 8). The hunting operator changes the priorities between them due to the random A and C parameters and the occupancy probability values of the dominated grid cells. The hunting operator for the area coverage problem is defined in (equation 6.1) and (equation 6.2). The robot's next position is either alpha, beta, or delta cell with the maximum value of $X_{1,i}$, $X_{2,i}$, $X_{3,i}$, where i is the number of robots.

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\alpha,i} &= |C_1 \cdot P_{\alpha,i}(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y}) - P_i(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y})| \\ D_{\beta,i} &= |C_2 \cdot P_{\beta,i}(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y}) - P_i(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y})| \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

$$D_{\delta,i} = |C_3 \cdot P_{\delta,i}(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y}) - P_i(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y})|$$

$$\begin{aligned} X_{1,i} &= P_{\alpha,i}(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y}) - A_1 \cdot D_{\alpha,i} \\ X_{2,i} &= P_{\beta,i}(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y}) - A_2 \cdot D_{\beta,i} \\ X_{3,i} &= P_{\delta,i}(occ_{x+\Delta x,y+\Delta y}) - A_3 \cdot D_{\delta,i} \end{aligned} \quad (6.2)$$

In the original GWO, the solution is the mean value of X_1 , X_2 , and X_3 . It is related to the natural behavior of a wolf pack that uses the intelligence of dominant agents. However, it is not required in the target selection problem to find the average robot positions among the alpha, beta, and delta grid cells. By taking this into consideration, the next robot position $X(t + 1)$ is the maximum value among $X_{1,i}$, $X_{2,i}$, and $X_{3,i}$.

Table 6.1 Coordinated multi-robot exploration with Grey Wolf Optimizer

-
- 1: Initialization the number of robots nRbt and iterations t, sensor range, initial position
 - 2: Set utility of unknown space 1
 - 3: while t is not over do
 - 4: for all nRbt
 - 5: Set coordinates of V_c
 - 6: Calculate cost of V_c
 - 7: Subtract U_c^i and V_c
 - 8: Find α, β, δ wolves among values of step 7
 - 9: Find $D_\alpha, D_\beta, D_\delta, X_1, X_2, X_3$
 - 10: Find $X(t + 1)$ as $\max(X_1, X_2, X_3)$
 - 11: Change robot position $X(t+1)$
 - 12: Reduce U_c^i on $X(t+1)$
 - 13: end for
 - 14: Calculate a, A, C parameters
 - 15: end while
-

When the robot gets the next selected position (line 11), the utility values of the neighbor cells are reduced. At the end of this, new values for the random parameters a, A, and C are generated for

the next iteration.

The hybrid stochastic exploration seeks to search uncertainties through the exploration process in the same manner that CME does. This works because the unexplored cells have greater utility values than those of the explored cells. When the costs with minimal values are subtracted from the utilities of the unexplored cells, the maximal values become attractive targets for the next robot positions. This principle is valid for both methods. However, the proposed hybrid stochastic method has three best options that can change the hierarchical order according to the stochastic parameters. It means that the maximal value may have a beta or delta position, not only alpha, as it is in the CME.

6.3 MOGWO exploration algorithm Based on Multi-robot System

In this section, we describe the proposed multi-robot exploration based on MOGWO optimization. First, we define the optimization problems in the exploration. As mentioned above, there are two objective functions for which the study tries to find an optimal solution. Then, the second subsection presents the approach for solving the problems using the MOGWO exploration algorithm.

6.3.1 Mathematical formulation of MOOPs in the multi-robot exploration

The process of searching uncertainties by a team of robots can be considered a multi-tasking system. Each robot receives the sensor reading data and upgrades the probabilities of the grid occupancy in the map. One robot should have the same task as another robot in the multi-robot system, wherein the task can be any of the following: scanning the environment using sensors, avoiding obstacles and collisions with other robots, seeking to explore new terrain, and increasing the accuracy of the map. It means that together, each single robot should provide good implementation as a multi-robot system satisfying the multi-objective functions for obtaining the best solutions.

In this paper, we formulated the objective functions of the exploration as follows:

$$\text{Maximize: } f_1 \rightarrow \text{number of explored cells} \quad (6.3)$$

$$\text{Minimize: } f_2 \rightarrow \text{probability values } P(\text{occ}_{x,y}) \quad (6.4)$$

Subject to:

$$i \geq (\text{total number of cells} - \text{total number of obstacle cells}) / \text{number of robots} \quad (6.5)$$

$$wp_w \geq \text{number of robots}^3 \quad (6.6)$$

$$wp_w \leq \text{total number of cells} - \text{total number of obstacle cells} \quad (6.7)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} i &= \text{number of iterations} \\ wp_w &= \text{number of waypoints} \end{aligned}$$

The first objective function in equation 6.3 tries to maximize the search space by visiting various numbers of cells in the map. In a good scenario, robots should avoid explored cells. The waypoints in MOGWO exploration allow to save the direction to the unexplored part of the map. However, there are some constraints for a successful search. For example, the number of waypoints should not be too small and big. In case, it is small, robots will stay in one point, because they do not have the tasks to drive next waypoints. If it is bigger than the total number of cells in a map, then, a robot will drive around one place longer than it is needed.

After the map is explored, the second objective function tries to improve the map accuracy by reducing the probability values of the grid cells. It means once a sensor beam touches a grid cell, the cell is marked as explored. However, a sensor does not have the same straight of a signal. In the robot position, the probability value has the lowest value. In frontier cells, the values are higher according to the power of a signal.

In the subsection below, the MOGWO exploration algorithm is described extensively.

6.3.2 The proposed MOGWO exploration algorithm

The objective functions in equations 6.3 and 6.4 defined the issues of the exploration in this study. For such problems, there is no single solution, which satisfies all objectives simultaneously at one time. It is not possible to explore new cells and to visit explored cells at the same time. Based on the GWO parameter a , the search process was divided into two parts. When $a > 1$, it searches new waypoints. When $a < 1$, the process turns for improving the map accuracy. Thus, the approach

serves two MOOPs in a single run-time.

Table 6.2 demonstrates the MOGWO exploration for the multi-robot system. The process begins with the random initialization of waypoints in the search space. Their positions are set only once in the first iteration and will not be upgraded throughout the whole exploration. In line 1, it was noted that the number of waypoints should be higher than $nRbt^3$ because each robot needs at least three of the best solutions α, β, γ for the search.

Table 6. 2 The pseudocode of the proposed MOGWO exploration

```

1: Set waypoints  $wp_w$  randomly in unknown space ( $wp > nRbt^3$ )
2: Set the archive is empty
3: Set initial robot position  $r_j$  ( $j = nRbt$ )
4: Initialize a, A, C
5: while i is not over do
6:   Update A, C
7:   Set the archive is empty
8:   for j = 1: nRbt
9:     Find current position  $x, y$  of  $r_1, r_2, r_3$ 
10:    Find frontier point  $Vn_{x,y}$  ( $n=1, \dots, 8$ ) of  $r_j$ 
11:    Insert rays to the map from  $x, y$  position
12:    Calculate the distances by the objective function ( $f_1$ )  $wp_w$ 
13:    Calculate the probability values by objective function ( $f_2$ ) for  $wp_w$ 
14:    if  $a \geq 1$ 
15:      if  $wp_w$  is explored
16:        Then, to increase  $wp_w$  cost
17:      if else  $wp_w$  is unexplored
18:        Then,  $wp_w$  cost
19:    end if
20:    Find minimum  $wp_\alpha, wp_\beta, wp_\delta$  costs and save in archive
21:    Find  $D_\alpha, D_\beta, D_\delta$  of  $r_j$  by equation 2
22:    Find  $X_1, X_2, X_3$  and  $X(i + 1)$  by equations 3 and 4
23:    Find  $r_j(i + 1) = \min(\text{eucl\_dist}[Vn_{x,y}, X(i + 1)])$ 

```

```

24:     end if
25:     if a<=1
26:         Divide probability cost by distance cost
27:         Find maximum  $wp_\alpha$ ,  $wp_\beta$ ,  $wp_\delta$  costs and save in archive
28:         Find  $r_j(i + 1) = \min(\text{eucl\_dist}[Vn_{x,y}, wp_\alpha])$ 
29:     end if
30: end for
31: Reduce a
32: show map
33: end while

```

The proposed algorithm uses the archive for the same purposes as MOGWO does. It allows the storage of the non-dominated solution, which prevents the repeated selection of the same waypoint by the robots. For each iteration in the loop, the robots upgrade the positions, the GWO parameters, and the positions and probability costs of the frontier cells (lines 9, 10).

Two objective functions are used for all stages (lines 12,13). The first one calculates the distances between waypoints and robots. The second objective function computes the probability values in the waypoint positions. Thus, the waypoints have distance costs of f_1 and probability costs f_2 .

Lines 14—24 show the exploration stage for $a \geq 1$. At first, it needs to divide the waypoints into explored and unexplored ones due to the probability costs in lines 15—19. Then, it can select the unexplored wp_α , wp_β , and wp_γ according to the distance costs (Figure 6.1). In lines 21 and 22, it computes the position $X(i + 1)$. However, the robots cannot jump physically to the position, thus, the frontier cell, which is the closest to $X(i + 1)$, is selected for the next robot position.

Lines 25—28 illustrate the exploitation stage for $a \leq 1$. It divides the probability cost f_2 by the distance cost f_1 . After, it finds the maximum value of the result in line 26 and saves it in the archive. The next robot position is one of the frontier cells, which is closest to the alpha waypoint.

Figure 6. 1 MOGWO exploration: a) selection the closest waypoints wp_α , wp_β , wp_γ among wp_w ; b) the waypoints that are located in explored space have the lowest interest to be selected for the robot than waypoints in unknown space; c) the best waypoints of one robots should not be duplicated for another robot

In line 30, the a parameter is reduced from 2 to 0 iteratively. Lastly, the map is upgraded by all robots in the end of iteration.

The implementation results are performed in the next section. The multi-robot exploration by MOGWO algorithm obtained notable results, which can be observed in various conditions by adjusting the numbers of waypoints and iterations.

6.4 GWO exploration algorithm Based on Mobile-robot System

Table 6.3 demonstrates the proposed GWO exploration algorithm based on the frontier-based technique and single robot motion.

The stochastic coefficients A and C are computed in each iteration controlling the exploration and exploitation phases in the GWO exploration (line 3). When sensor rays return a distance less than the maximum sensing range d , it will make α , β , and δ groups of f points (line 6). The grouping is necessary for selecting regions of non-dominated f points. Since the frontier points are generated by a laser sensor, they are naturally concentrated very close to each other. It assumes m numbers of f points in each group. Line 7 finds mean frontier points f_α , f_β , and f_δ in groups by the distance cost f_c values. Figure 6.2 shows the selection of f_α , f_β , and f_δ . It must be noted that all frontier points of current and previous time steps take part in the selection.

Table 6.3 GWO robot exploration algorithm

1:	Initialize a, $\text{adamp} = a/\text{maxItern}$
2:	while j is not over
3:	Calculate A1, A2, A3, C1, C2, C3 by (6) and (7)
4:	if $G_{dist} < \text{max sensor range}$
5:	Ascending sort f points by their costs
6:	Take first, second, third m points in α , β , δ groups from the sorted array
7:	Find mean f points in α , β , δ groups as $f_\alpha, f_\beta, f_\delta$
8:	$D_{\alpha,\beta,\delta} = C_{1,2,3} \cdot f_{\alpha,\beta,\delta} - xy_{robot} $
9:	$X_{1,2,3} = f_{\alpha,\beta,\delta} - A_{1,2,3} \cdot D_{\alpha,\beta,\delta}$
10:	Find next global point $g(i+1)$ by (11)
11:	end
12:	$a = a - \text{adamp}$
13:	end while

Afterwards, the distances D_α , D_β , and D_δ can be computed based on the current robot position and non-dominated frontier points in line 8. The global waypoint $g(i+1)$ can be estimated from the X_1 , X_2 , and X_3 values.

In the original GWO algorithm, the dominated ω agents are obliged to upgrade their positions based on the α , β , and δ solutions. However, in the proposed GWO exploration algorithm, the dominated agent is the robot that should follow the non-dominated solutions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.2 Frontier points at iteration j . a) The classification in three groups according to the distance costs between the robot position and the frontier point positions. The lowest cost values are in the alpha group, the highest cost values are in the delta group. b) The selection of one frontier point from each group, which has an average distance cost

The presented GWO exploration algorithm prevents the parameter a in line 12 to decrease. When the value a is less than 1, the global waypoints as goals appear quite close to the robot. These short drives lead to frequent changes in robot direction movement, which is energy and time consuming for the mobile robot system.

6.5 WO exploration algorithm Based on Mobile-robot System

The WO exploration algorithm begins with the generation of the parameters (Table 6.4, lines 1 to 4). Then, it creates X^* group consisting of m points, which are obtained from the first elements of sorted array in lines 6 and 7. The mean frontier point of X^* group is defined as f^* point. The random frontier point f_{rand} is chosen from all available frontier points except the points of X^* group (line 9). Figure 6.3 (a) shows the selection of f^* and f_{rand} points.

Table 6.4 WO robot exploration algorithm

```

1: Initialize a, adamp = a/maxItern, b = 1
2: while j is not over
3:   Calculate A, C by (6) and (7)
4:   Find l, p
5:   if  $G_{dist} < \text{max sensor range}$ 
6:     Ascending sort  $f$  points by their costs
7:     Take first  $m$  frontier points in  $X^*$  group
8:     Find mean  $f$  point in  $X^*$  group as best whale  $f^*$ 
9:     Find random  $f$  point among all points as  $f_{rand}$ 
10:    if  $p < 0.5$ 
11:      if  $|A| < 1$ 
12:         $D = |C \cdot f^* - xy_{robot}|$ 

```



```

13:         Find  $g(i + 1)$  by equation (5.11)
14:     elseif  $|A| \geq 1$ 
15:          $D = |C \cdot f_{rand} - xy_{robot}|$ 
16:         Find  $g(i + 1)$  by equation (5.13)
17:     end
18: elseif  $p \geq 0.5$ 
19:      $D = |f^* - xy_{robot}|$ 
20:     Find  $g(i + 1)$  by equation (5.15)
21: end
22: end
23:  $a = a - \text{adamp}$ 
24: end

```

When the best and random whale solutions are found, the next $g(i + 1)$ can be computed using equations (5.11), (5.13), or (5.15) in lines 13, 16, and 20, respectively. The decision on what method is applied in the bubble-net hunting and which phase is the search (exploration or exploitation) depends on the p and A parameters.

The proposed WO exploration algorithm prevents the parameter a (line 23) to decrease by the same reason as the GWO exploration approach.

Figure 6.3 a) Representation of the best whale (f^*) and random whale (f_{rand}) solutions among the frontier points; b) Illustration of the change of stochastic parameter A during 2300 iterations when parameter a decreases two times from 2 to 0

6.6 PSO exploration algorithm Based on Mobile-robot System

Table 6.5 presents the PSO exploration algorithm. The PSO is activated when a robot faces obstacles, in the same way that the GWO and WO exploration algorithms are activated. It starts to search a global solution P_g among $f(k)$ points. The P_g value in the PSO exploration algorithm is a frontier point with a minimum distance cost f_c , which is denoted as f_{min} point (line 4). Then, the velocity V estimates the divergent step size based on the personal best f , global best f_{min} , and the robot location. It considers the personal best P_i as the current position of f in x and y axes. In line 6, the new point $x(k)$ is found. Figure 6.4 (a) depicts the f_{min} and $x(k)$ selections.

Table 6.5 PSO exploration algorithm

1:	Initialize w , $wdamp = 0.99$, $c_1 = 2$, $c_2 = 2$
2:	while j in not over
3:	if $G_{dist} < \text{max sensor range}$
4:	Find P_g of f points as f_{min}
5:	$V(k) = w \cdot V_k^{j-1} + c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (f(k)_{xy} - xy_{robot}) + c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (f_{min} - xy_{robot})$
6:	$x(k) = V(k) + f(k)_{xy} $ by equation 5.2
7:	Find $x(k)_c$ using Euclidean metric between $f(k)_{xy}$ and $x(k)$
8:	Ascending sort by $x(k)_c$
9:	Take first m sorted f points
10:	Find mean f point as $g(i + 1)$
11:	end if
12:	$w = w \cdot wdamp$
13:	end while

In line 7, it computes the distance costs $x(k)_c$ for the frontier points and newly obtained $x(k)$ points. It needs to be emphasized that the PSO exploration approach searches distance costs two times: 1) from the robot position to the frontier point and 2) from the frontier point to the new x point. In lines 8 and 9, it obtains m frontier points with minimum $x(k)_c$ values. Then, it selects the mean frontier point as the next global waypoint where the robot will drive next (Figure 6.4, b).

Figure 6.4 The PSO exploration algorithm: a) the velocities (dash lines) and their $x(k)$ points; b) selection of the global point $g(i+1)$ based on the minimum distance cost of $V(k)$, where i is the order number of global waypoints

The process continues until the time is over or the indoor environment is fully explored.

6.7 Conclusion

In chapter 6, the methodologies of the nature-inspired exploration algorithms were presented based on GWO, MOGWO, WO, and PSO algorithms for single mobile robot system and multi-robot systems. The robot position and sensor data were considered in the proposed techniques as the input parameters.

The GWO exploration algorithms for the mobile and multi-robot systems explore the uncertainties by hierarchy structure of alpha, beta, and gamma solutions. It can be said that the GWO exploration is led by the three best solutions, which are calculated based on the distance costs. The MOGWO exploration algorithm pursuits the two goals in the exploration. The first one is to visit all environment by the multi-robot system and the second one is to enhance the map accuracy.

The PSO exploration algorithm is guided by the best solution, which has the minimum distance cost by the single robot. Each frontier point has its velocities and costs. The global waypoint is the minimum value of frontier point cost and velocity.

The WO exploration algorithm is led by the random and the best solutions. The global

waypoint is the average distance of minimum ten best solution when the spiral hunting method is activated and the random frontier point when shrinking method is activated.

In each nature-inspired exploration algorithm, the stochastic parameters play the important role for the robot system. The trajectories of robot motion is unique in each simulation run and could not be repeated again. In the Chapter 7, this simulation results and the real experiment will prove the efficiency on the proposed stochastic exploration concepts.

Chapter 7

Simulation and Experiment results

7.1 Motivation

This chapter proposes the simulation results of the nature-inspired exploration algorithms for mobile robot exploration problems. Navigation with uncertain conditions in the absence of initial parameters is a situation wherein precomputation and prediction are impossible for a robot. Therefore, this study proposes to solve the exploration problems using stochastic optimization techniques. Driving to the unknown areas, the robot updates the frontier line of sensor visibility during the exploration mission. The points of the frontier line are assumed as the swarm population with their own positions and costs, which allow the computation of the next global waypoint. In this chapter, the simulation results of exploration algorithms are presented based on GWO, MOGWO, PSO, and WO algorithms. At first, the simulations are implemented and evaluated using the proposed algorithms in a created environment. Then, it will be proved the algorithm's effectiveness in real world constraints using MATLAB-ROS integration.

7.2 Simulations of the proposed GWO exploration algorithms

This section presents the simulation of the hybrid coordinated exploration based on GWO in two maps: ordinary and complex. The proposed hybrid method was compared with the original CME, which we seek to outperform.

Considering that the robots can move in an arbitrary manner, the map coverage is the primary issue and the principal criterion for this type of system. With the aim of analyzing the simulation results for the two approaches, the following equation 7.1 computes the percentage of total explored grid cells (M_c):

$$M_c = \frac{U_{unexp} - U_{exp}}{U_{unexp}} \times 100\% \quad (7.1)$$

where U_{unexp} is the total unexplored utility values that are free from obstacles and U_{exp} is the total explored utility values. The comparison between the proposed hybrid stochastic exploration and CME can be done based on the M_c value after the simulation is completed.

The same map parameters were set for both methods in the ordinary and complex maps. The parameters are the number of iterations, obstacles, number of robots, map size, sensor range, and initial robot positions. By taking into consideration that we are comparing the deterministic and stochastic approaches, the former needs to run only once, i.e., the trajectory of the robot's motion stays invariant when the map remains the same, whereas the proposed stochastic method requires finding the best result among the simulation runs.

7.2.1 Ordinary Map

An ordinary map is an environment with the minimum number of obstacles. It allows robots to have more freeways for motion that makes it easier for them to diverge from each other.

Figure 7.1 illustrates the results of the explorations by two methods where three robots have different path colors. The CME achieved slightly better exploration (97.31%) than the proposed hybrid stochastic method on the ordinary map. With 100 iterations and 20 simulation runs, the

stochastic approach gave different results each time due to the random A and C values. In Figure 7.1, maps (b), (c), and (d) show the map coverage of the proposed approach at 69.72% (worst), 85.98%, and 95.83% (best), respectively.

Figure 7.1 The map coverage for the CME (a) at 97.31% and the hybrid stochastic exploration based on GWO and CME at 69.72% (b), 85.98% (c), and 95.83% (d). The number of iterations is 100

In the CME, the robots always move toward the maximum utility values (α). On the other hand, in the proposed hybrid stochastic exploration the robots can seek any of the three maximum utility values (α , β , and δ) depending on the A and C parameters, which was observed through the 20 simulations mentioned above. The map coverage was classified into three categories: “0 to 79%”, “80 to 89%”, and “90% and higher”. Figure 7.2 shows that out of the 20 simulation runs, only one of them has the worst map coverage wherein the robots chose the β positions mostly. Likewise, the

other 16 simulation runs in the “90% and higher” category showed that the robots favored mostly β positions instead of the α positions, which is typical of CME. In the second category, the δ positions dominated the runs.

Figure 7.2 The histogram of the hybrid stochastic exploration based on GWO and CME using 20 simulation runs. The subcategories belong to the alpha, beta, and delta cell decisions

The performance of the hybrid stochastic exploration may be improved when the number of iterations is increased to 130 (Figure 7.3). As seen, the hybrid stochastic method showed greater map coverage than the deterministic exploration in some runs.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7.3 The map coverage comparison of CME and the hybrid stochastic exploration based on GWO and CME for the ordinary map with $t = 100$ (a) and $t = 130$ (b) iterations through 20 simulation runs. For 100 iterations, the maximum percentage belongs to the CME at 97.31%, while for 130 iterations, the hybrid stochastic exploration gives the maximum value at 98.68%

7.2.2 Complex Map

Here we consider the algorithm performance in cluttered environments using four maps as shown in Figure 7.4 and 7.5. Both the CME (Figure 7.4) and hybrid stochastic algorithms (Figure 7.5) were tested for the percentage of map coverage for complex areas.

Map 3: 70.71%

Map 4: 96.32%

Figure 7.4 The exploration results of the CME simulations with 100 iterations. Map 1 was interrupted on the 57th iteration because one robot was baffled by another robot on the upper right corner. In map 2, two of the robots could not get out from the left partition (bottleneck space), which limited the search of the unexplored space. Map 3 was explored with 70.71% coverage. The coverage is almost complete on map 4

Map 1: 96.97%

Map 2: 99.52%

Figure 7.5 The results of the hybrid stochastic exploration with 100 iterations. All maps have efficient exploration results, although the robot tried to go through the horizontal obstacle on the upper portion of map 4 to find a free path. It is noted that a narrow corridor may be a point of improvement for the method

The CME (Figure 7.4) showed a high map coverage only in map 4. Its performance in the other maps was less efficient, and it did not allow improvement in the next iterations because of the invariant nature of the deterministic method. In contrast, the proposed hybrid stochastic exploration based on GWO and CME allowed the search for solutions even after relaunching the simulation runs. The four map results (Figure 7.5) demonstrated the strong capability of the proposed hybrid method for the coverage of varying complex maps.

7.2.3 The feature of the proposed Multi-robot GWO exploration

In using the hybrid approach, the random parameters as additional weights for utilities oblige the robots to estimate the next position, which can lead to obstacle collision problems in some situations. This problem occurs when a robot is surrounded with the same utility values equal to zero and/or obstacles of neighbor cells. In Figure 7.4, map 1 showed that a similar circumstance also happens for CME. The difference between the two approaches, however, lies on the capability of the hybrid stochastic approach to search for a new solution with random values for the A and C parameters, which is not possible for CME or other deterministic approaches.

The number of the simulation runs for the four maps in Figure 7.5 is presented in Table 7.1. In

order to obtain ten successful runs of map coverage passing 100 iterations, the total number of failed simulation runs are 21, 4, and 14 for maps 1, 3, and 4 respectively. The hybrid approach gave its best performance in map 2, where all 10 runs were successful (0 failed runs) and the map coverage is the highest at 99.52%.

Table 7.1 The number of aborted simulation runs of the hybrid stochastic exploration on four complex maps

Map 1	21
Map 2	0
Map 3	4
Map 4	14

7.3 Multi-robot MOGWO exploration

A. Experiment Setup

In this section, we implemented the proposed MOGWO exploration and analyzed the obtained results. As alternatives, there are varying parameters for testing the simulation performance such as the number of waypoints and the number of iterations. The parameters are used to test the algorithm performance in several ways. However, some parameters were maintained as constant throughout all the simulation runs (see Table 7.2).

Table 7.2 Experimental parameters

Parameters	Value
Initial poses	$r_1 = (5,5), r_2 = (7,9), r_3 = (4,9)$
Map size	5×5
Obstacle Width	0.5

Ray Length	1.5
Probabilities of occupancy cells	$P(\text{robot}_{R_{x,y}R}) = 0.0010$ $P(\text{obstacles}_{R_{x,y}R}) = 0.9990$ $P(\text{unexplored}_{R_{x,y}R}) = 0.5000$ $P(\text{unexplored}_{R_{x,y}R}) > P(\text{explored}_{R_{x,y}R}) > P(\text{robot}_{R_{x,y}R})$

The major goal, which we seek to attain, is to know how many iterations and how many waypoints are needed for efficient exploration. If the number of iterations is too low, the robots do not have time to explore the entire map physically considering that the size of the step in each iteration is unchanged. The same is true for the number of waypoints. They should be enough for free robot driving in the environment. In the next subsection, the experiments with certain constraints are presented, and the Pareto optimal set is proposed for the selection of the optimal solution of the environment.

B. Simulation results

The MOGWO exploration algorithm brings the experiment analysis in two aspects: how it explores and how it improves the accuracy of the map. The experiment constraints influence the results of these problems. Due to the GWO stochastic parameters, the decision-making process can be different in each simulation run. It leads us to test the algorithm performance several times with the same constraints. Based on the experiment parameters in Table 7.3, it can be calculated in equation (7.2) that the iteration number should not be less than 60 and more than 120. And, for the waypoints, the range should be from 60 to 150 for three robots in certain map size. In this study, we selected the parameters as 60, 80, 100, and 120 iterations and 60, 80, 100, and 150 waypoints. Table 7.3 shows the results of map coverage in percentage, which is computed using the following equation:

$$\text{Map coverage (\%)} = \left(100 - \frac{\sum \text{cell probability values after run time}}{\sum \text{cell probability values before run time}} \right) \times 100 \quad (7.2)$$

In the table, it was emphasized that, for example, the maximum map coverage with certain sequence of decisions and the constraints, 60 iterations by 60 waypoints, is 92.36%. Furthermore, the highest result from among all the set of constraints used is 99.47% at the maximum allowable constraints.

Table 7. 3 Simulation results of 30 run times in the number of iterations: 60, 80 100, 120

# waypoints	Number of iterations							
	60		80		100		120	
60	90.17	92.36	92.42	91.16	91.51	85.93	98.21	95.81
	82.08	85.55	88.27	90.20	93.54	95.92	95.38	89.61
	89.10	85.36	87.91	87.90	96.07	93.47	89.62	89.03
	86.58	85.52	90.72	91.70	92.07	92.30	94.26	98.02
	90.62	86.79	94.03	91.11	90.33	87.92	96.59	92.89
	90.01	82.14	89.21	88.30	95.22	91.70	95.22	93.38
	87.78	88.84	93.94	88.85	95.30	88.25	96.33	91.68
	88.00	86.03	93.18	90.65	95.76	88.89	94.10	95.99
	87.62	89.68	85.15	92.61	93.60	93.46	91.63	93.65
	81.42	88.60	94.39	89.23	92.21	90.34	91.60	91.22
	92.15	88.48	93.05	90.43	92.77	92.81	97.20	94.28
	85.58	84.89	91.99	89.39	91.31	94.86	91.69	95.57
	84.16	86.74	93.40	94.95	93.50	88.99	95.84	92.64
	86.61	83.59	95.50	93.14	91.83	96.57	95.48	94.63
	91.63	84.70	92.40	95.23	94.61	92.46	97.47	97.33
80	90.53	89.00	96.28	93.19	90.16	95.48	96.68	94.28
	89.24	90.01	94.32	93.73	94.30	90.94	86.57	97.28
	90.24	89.59	94.72	92.70	96.16	86.94	95.38	94.13
	88.92	88.62	95.38	96.69	96.42	96.67	98.40	94.95
	86.90	87.66	91.98	89.37	94.17	94.85	97.86	94.07
	84.95	91.15	90.90	92.56	93.84	95.92	95.16	96.54
	89.38	87.89	92.05	93.81	96.61	94.65	96.14	95.16
	88.41	88.39	92.11	90.56	94.66	96.51	97.52	94.90
	90.47	87.61	97.01	94.86	95.20	92.80	94.76	97.84
	82.78	87.21	95.15	94.39	94.89	93.81	96.92	95.63
	82.00	82.86	90.49	93.43	96.76	93.81	94.72	92.89
	91.21	84.37	91.49	95.56	96.72	95.43	95.91	96.74
	89.07	89.44	93.47	90.93	92.19	95.63	94.38	94.67

	88.21 87.64	89.54 89.23	91.19 92.93	94.18 88.49	91.21 93.71	94.38 92.50	98.01 98.45	97.78 92.14
100	90.12	87.49	95.34	89.59	95.11	94.45	97.78	97.05
	90.16	88.19	93.45	92.88	96.69	97.29	95.14	97.48
	87.59	90.10	95.47	95.37	95.81	96.48	95.13	97.11
	89.32	92.26	97.58	96.16	93.90	96.97	96.86	98.48
	88.19	88.81	91.33	93.93	96.57	96.03	96.17	97.07
	87.18	89.89	93.17	95.23	94.61	97.52	96.51	98.17
	80.68	87.74	93.77	93.65	92.49	97.32	93.09	96.31
	89.14	89.01	95.73	95.55	95.99	96.97	97.09	96.16
	89.23	91.39	93.25	94.18	97.49	97.72	98.40	96.43
	84.98	88.36	94.71	95.08	97.27	95.42	97.24	96.49
	90.95	90.45	92.78	92.91	95.84	94.40	96.67	96.23
	87.77	89.86	91.44	86.62	97.11	92.47	95.15	97.56
	88.52	86.66	92.31	93.42	94.00	93.77	95.75	95.89
	88.18	91.14	92.71	92.62	95.49	97.95	96.38	99.03
86.81	89.48	94.45	94.70	95.40	97.09	94.30	98.03	
150	91.15	92.52	96.26	90.48	98.48	98.06	99.06	98.94
	92.83	91.41	94.41	95.21	98.41	96.60	98.96	95.48
	91.97	86.52	96.27	95.72	98.84	97.24	98.97	97.40
	92.14	85.72	95.38	93.91	95.91	95.21	98.21	98.15
	92.02	87.60	96.80	95.70	96.83	97.53	97.13	98.33
	89.30	91.56	95.75	94.94	97.71	97.34	98.11	97.54
	89.73	91.20	95.82	93.62	98.52	95.53	98.31	97.61
	84.98	88.67	96.76	91.84	98.54	96.67	96.17	98.19
	90.40	88.26	95.58	95.02	97.64	97.26	98.69	98.11
	90.52	80.15	96.50	95.98	93.97	96.51	97.26	98.63
	88.25	88.63	93.46	96.55	95.28	97.56	94.85	98.13
	92.41	93.22	95.52	95.62	96.43	96.52	98.26	98.92
	93.22	92.24	95.38	97.78	96.97	95.96	98.49	98.52
	88.31	90.85	94.24	93.77	98.27	98.78	97.71	99.47
91.21	86.41	95.94	91.67	96.67	97.27	98.94	98.04	

Figure 7.6 shows one of the simulation-runs with the constraints: 120 iterations and 150 waypoints. In the $a \geq 1$ stage, the environment was explored in 87.57% in the half of the total number of iterations. For the map in Figure 7.6, b, it can be concluded that the robots touched all the waypoints with the sensor rays. This means that the exploration ability of the algorithm is

satisfied in this stage. Figure 7.6, c demonstrates the completed result for the $a \leq 1$ stage with a total of 99.06% map coverage. The trajectories of the robots can be observed through the blue, red, and green colored lines in Figure 7.6, d.

Figure 7.6 The simulation of MOGWO exploration algorithm in a) iteration 1 with $a=2$; b) iteration 61 with $a=1$; c) the last iteration 120 with $a=0.016$; d) the trajectories of three robots

The decision-making process of each robot is presented in Figure 7.7. The values of alpha solutions in the simulation above (Figure 7.6) vary for the two stages: exploration and exploitation. It can be seen that when $a \geq 1$, the trend goes up to maximum values, and when $a \leq 1$, the simulation tries to achieve the minimum values.

Figure 7.7 Decision-making process of alpha solutions: a) robot 1; b) robot 2; c) robot 3

Table 7.3 shows numerous exploration results, which are categorized by constraints. Considering only on the percentage of map coverage, it is obvious that 99.47% is the best performance. However, the exploration with 120 iterations and 150 waypoints as constraints takes the longest time, which means it is not the optimal solution.

In this study, we take two factors that are important for the exploration: map coverage and time. In Figure 7.8, we searched for the trade-offs between the minimum number of iterations and the maximum number of map coverage. The plot was made based on the data in Table 7.3. The results with 120 and 60 run times are extreme solutions, which are very long and short for the exploration. Thus, the solutions belong to the Pareto optimal front, which lies between two lines.

Figure 7.8 Pareto optimal set of MOGWO exploration algorithm

7.4 Simulation of the Single Mobile-robot GWO, WO, and PSO exploration algorithms

In this section, the proposed GWO, WO, and PSO exploration algorithms are validated through simulated experiments. The same map size, time steps, sensor model, and environment blueprint were used for the exploration algorithms in order to compare accurately their performance. The general parameters used in the simulations are summarized in Table 7.4. The quantity of iterations has been chosen heuristically according to the map and robot step sizes.

Table 7.4 Simulation parameters

Map size	20 × 30 m
Max sensor range (d)	5 m
Threshold for obstacle avoidance (V_{dist})	2.5 m
Lookahead distance for obstacle avoidance (L)	2 m
Max iteration number ($nItern$)	2300

Max number of sensing rays (s)	50
------------------------------------	----

The simulations were implemented using Robotics System Toolbox, which is an integrated tool between MATLAB and Robot Operating System (ROS). The integration enables the simulation of a robot and laser sensor models in the created environments (Figure 7.9) and the simultaneous updating of the binary occupancy map while the robot drives. The special functions of the BinaryOccupancyMap class permits the extraction of the positions of frontier points and finding the intersection points of rays and obstacles. The Pure Pursuit controller of Robotics System Toolbox was utilized in our simulations, in order to calculate linear and angle velocities from the current robot location to waypoint position $g(i)$ in each iteration [128].

Figure 7.9 Created map of the environment and simulated driving and sensing robot model

The presented algorithms were tested several times in simulated world conditions. By the nature of stochastic approaches, it is assumed that varied results can be obtained in each simulation run. Consequently, the set of experiments were carried out and demonstrated in this section for a better analysis of the algorithm performances. Furthermore, traveled distances, number of waypoints, map coverage and others, are used to measure the exploration results of the bio-stochastic techniques as the evaluation indicators. The map coverage metrics is defined as follows:

$$M_{exp}(\%) = \left(100 - \frac{\sum cells_{init} - \sum cells_{exp}}{\sum cells_{init}} \right) \times 100 \quad (7.3)$$

where $cells_{init}$ is the initial total number of unexplored grid cells excluding the occupied ones

by obstacles and $cells_{exp}$ is the total number of explored cells after the exploration without obstacle cells.

In order to know which action, the robot takes throughout the simulations, the parameters exploring new cells P_{exp} or avoiding obstacles P_{avoid} are presented as follows:

$$P_{exp}(\%) = (c_{exp}/nIntern) \times M_{exp} \quad (7.4)$$

$$P_{avoid}(\%) = (c_{avoid}/nIntern) \times M_{exp} \quad (7.5)$$

where c_{exp} and c_{avoid} are counters, which are increased by one in each iteration if the decisions have already been made.

The performances of GWO, WO, and PSO exploration algorithms are presented in three stages of iterations across the process: 250, 1000, and 2300 iterations. While the robot drives through the indoor environment of Figure 679, another map of Figure 7.10 with full uncertainties is updated following the global and local waypoints. Three simulation results are presented with full map coverages at the end of the iterations for explicit comparisons.

After 250 iterations, it can be observed that the number of global waypoints is highest in the GWO exploration because the robot reached them quickly due to the short distances. This means that the proposed GWO exploration algorithm diverges slightly compared with the WO and PSO exploration approaches. Thus, the frequent changes in the direction to the global waypoint affect the efficiency of robot driving.

After 1000 iterations, the number of local waypoints in the GWO exploration is greater than in the two other approaches. The local waypoints are activated to prevent the robot from colliding with the obstacles. At the same time, it means that switching the direction into the local waypoints influences the exploration efficiency as well. During the collision avoidance, the robot may avoid an obstacle by clearing the way or it may circle around an obstacle repeatedly by returning to this problem again.

When the robot decision-making behavior was evaluated through the simulation, it was found that the GWO exploration has 75.56% searching actions in 2300 iterations (see Table 7.5). This means that the result of the close located global waypoints shows that the robot does not need to walk repeatedly in explored areas due to the appropriate locations of waypoints. The WO and PSO exploration values are lower at 70.34% and 68.43%, respectively.

Table 7.5 The comparison of the evaluation parameters

	GWO exploration of Figure 7.10	WO exploration of Figure 7.10	PSO exploration of Figure 7.10
P_{exp}	75.56%	70.34%	68.43%
P_{avoid}	44.43%	27.17%	24.82%
Traveled distance	132.98 m	133.06 m	126.80 m
Number of waypoints	109	86	40

Evaluation of the traveled distance and obstacle avoidance shows that the main disadvantages of GWO exploration is the obstacle avoidance part. A high P_{exp} value and the long distance traveled, 132.98 meters, imply that the robot tries to solve obstacle avoidance issue often. 133.06 meters for WO exploration is a significant distance as well, but the low values of obstacle avoidance and exploration actions can be interpreted as the robot wasting time mostly for walking along explored areas. The same conclusion can be said for PSO exploration.

GWO exploration

Iteration: 250

Iteration: 1000

Iteration: 2300

WO exploration

Iteration: 250

Iteration: 1000

Iteration: 2300

PSO exploration

Iteration: 250

Iteration: 1000

Iteration: 2300

Figure 7.10 The simulation results of the proposed nature-inspired algorithms for the mobile robot exploration with full map coverages. The colored circles mean the local points and the others are the global waypoints

It must be pointed out that the WO exploration algorithm has one significant drawback, which can be seen at the lower, right corner of Figure 7.10 after 2300 iterations. The congestion of global waypoints at one place happens only at the end of the iterations when the robot cannot reach the last frontier points. Depending on the A value, the random or best solutions can be chosen among whale agents (frontier points). A random solution can choose a frontier point arbitrarily and oblige the robot to move to another area while ignoring the distance cost. Then, the robot will not be stuck in one place by the global waypoints. In the case of the best whale solution, it cannot guide the robot to the last frontier points at the end of the simulation because the distance costs show that the decision is not the best.

At the end of the simulations for 2300 iterations, all three of the proposed nature-inspired exploration techniques were able to solve the mobile robot exploration problem with 100% of map coverage, although, the performances of the algorithms are not identical.

To compare the average performance of the proposed stochastic approaches, the simulations were run ten times for each one (Figure 7.11). For the PSO algorithm performance, the value could reach as low as 75% in terms of map coverage, leading to an average value of 83%. The highest average map coverage value belongs to the GWO exploration algorithms at 91.21%, including its superiority compared to the WO and PSO exploration algorithms.

Figure 7.11 Results of ten simulations of the GWO, WO, and PSO exploration algorithms

It can be concluded that the GWO exploration algorithm provides greater performance of map coverage in the general case. The PSO exploration gives the best exploration result in single cases, considering a few selected global and local waypoints and the short distance traveled by the mobile robot.

The simulation video of the GWO, WO, and PSO exploration algorithms is available on YouTube [129].

7.5 Experiment of the proposed GWO exploration algorithm using MATLAB and ROS integration and Turtlebot

In this section, the nature-inspired exploration approach is tested in real-world conditions. Two

experiments were conducted under two constraints: one is in a place with free straight path; another is in a t-shaped area (Figure 7.12). It should be emphasized that the map size is not initialized, and it extends while the robot drives. The initial position is not selected as well. When the experiment starts, the robot odometry is set at zero values.

Figure 7.12 The experiments using the proposed GWO exploration algorithm in two cases b) and d). The completed maps are illustrated in a) and c)

In the experiments, Turtlebot is employed, which is equipped with a Kinect sensor and onboard laptop with installed ROS. Our program in MATLAB on PC is subscribed on the Kinect sensor topic for reading laser sensor data with 57 degrees of horizontal angle view. The data as input allows calculating the Turtlebot's next position. The generation of new local point or global point is activated when the robot passes through certain distance thresholds. When the robot drives closer than 0.8 meter to an obstacle, then the new global point should be calculated based on the stochastic algorithms. When the threshold is less than 0.6 meter, the local point will help the robot to turn

away from obstacles. The threshold values have been chosen after several tests according to this environment blueprint. The experiments were recorded in a video [129] that shows how waypoints are switched and generated while the robot drives. However, it can also be seen in the video that the robot does not move smoothly. The robot makes pauses in each time step. This lack of fluency can be attributed to the execution delays due to the algorithm computations [108].

Analysis of the experimental runs shows that the proposed biologically inspired techniques can be successfully applied to the mobile robot exploration problem. The techniques can guide safely the robot to explore the uncertainties by constantly producing the global waypoints, which are computed based on the frontier line. Additionally, the real experiments proved that the aborted simulations in our previous studies [130], [131] were the shortcoming of obstacle avoidance maneuvers, which offered unsafe local waypoints. Since the obstacle avoidance mechanism was developed in this study, the issue was not detected in the simulated and real-world experiments.

In this study, the switching mechanism of the local and global points showed robust exploration results that can be further investigated by other stochastic optimization techniques in future studies [132].

7.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, the simulation results of the stochastic exploration algorithms were presented based on GWO, WO, and PSO for mobile robot system.

The algorithms compute global waypoints in unknown areas, which the robot tries to reach. The global waypoints were estimated according to the frontier point and present robot positions. During its crossing, the robot can collide with obstacles that it should avoid due to the local waypoints. This switching of global and local waypoints defines a decision-making mechanism in the exploration.

The simulation results demonstrate the comparisons among the bio-exploration algorithms based on the following evaluation parameters: map coverage, traveled distance, and number of global waypoints. The experiment in real world conditions using the GWO exploration algorithm proved that the stochastic algorithm can be applied to mobile exploration problem in robotics.

Chapter 8

Conclusions and Future Research

8.1 Summary of contributions

Exploration is one of the high-level behaviors in the mobile robotics: searching uncertainties and constructing a finite map. During the searching process, the robot controller has to handle the challenges by detection and avoiding the obstacles. The map representation is the way how to save the information about the environment by graph or by occupancy grids. The robot kinematics and the sensor vision effect on the strategy of exploration.

In this thesis, four nature-inspired techniques were proposed for the multi-mobile robot and single mobile robot exploration. The exploration properties were selected as following: 1) the differential drive based on the two standard wheels and one ball wheel; 2) laser scanner sensor; 3) probabilistic occupancy map and binary occupancy map; 4) centralized communication; 5) pure pursuing tracking algorithm; 6) MATLAB with Robotics System Toolbox and ROS.

The simulation results were compared by the evaluation such as map coverage, traveled distance, and number of global waypoints. The simulation shown that GWO exploration algorithm exceeds the others stochastic exploration algorithms in single and in general cases. It can be said that its average value of the best solutions leads the system efficiently. The second-best result in the simulation belongs to the PSO exploration algorithm due to its unpredictable performance in single case.

This thesis research belongs to the novel stochastic problem-solving techniques in the mobile robot exploration. The simulation results prove that the nature inspired algorithms can be applied successfully in the robotics particular for the wheeled mobile robot.

8.2 Direction of future research

The mobile robotics has various problems in navigation, communication, exploration, semantic learning environment and etc. There are still a lot of issues pursuing the autonomous motion. In the future works, the combination of the neural network-based platform and the nature inspired techniques is profit study for robotics community. In this unit, it supposed to apply the metaheuristic algorithms as optimization method for learning neural network replacing the classical backpropagation approach. It is worthy to note that this study is completely different direction that has its own map representation and vision method.

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Achievements

Journal

1. Albina, K., Lee, S.G. “Hybrid stochastic exploration using Grey Wolf optimizer and coordinated multi-robot exploration algorithms.” IEEE Access, 7, 2019, pp.14246-14255.
2. Kamalova, A., Navruzov, S., Qian, D. and Lee, S.G. “Multi-Robot exploration based on multi-objective grey wolf optimizer.” Applied Sciences, 9(14), 2019, p.2931

생체 모방 Metaheuristic 최적화 기법을 이용한 멀티 로봇 시스템의 Frontier 기반 탐사

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전기공학과 제어 및 전력 변환 전공

(지도교수 이 석 규)

요 약

모바일 로봇 시스템은 동작, 이동 경로 계획, 현재 위치 정보, 로봇 간의 대형, 목표 추적 및 탐색을 위해 지도가 필요하다. 예를 들어, 경로 계획 문제를 해결하려면 알려진 지도에서 로봇의 시작 및 목표 위치 좌표를 설정 한 다음 사용 가능한 짧은 이동 경로를 계산해야 한다. 로봇의 경로 계획 문제를 해결하기 위해 사전에 지도를 제공하거나 로봇이 탐사를 통해 해결해야 한다. 로봇의 자율 탐사는 로봇 공학의 기본 연구 문제로, 하나의 로봇으로 해결하거나 다중 로봇을 통한 상호간의 정보를 이용하여 해결 할 수 있다. 로봇의 탐사의 예로 바닥 청소, 행성 탐사, 수중 탐사 및 기타 널리 알려진 수색 및 구조 탐사 임무이며, 이는 응급 상황에서 인간에게 위협 할 수 있다. 본 연구는 모바일 로봇 시스템의 탐색에 관련 된 것 이다.

초기 지도정보가 없는 로봇은 불확실한 환경에서 탑재 된 센서들의 정보를 취합하기 위해 운행 되고 최종적으로 목표지점까지의 센서 정보를 취합하여 지도를 완성하게

된다. 하지만 지도를 완성하였지만 목표지점까지 최적의 시간으로 움직이는 로봇의 궤적을 만들지는 않는다. 예를 들어 로봇이 장애물을 만나서 선회하여 운행 하는 등의 불확실한 움직임으로 최적의 이동경로를 만들어 주는 것이 아니므로 로봇 궤적을 최적화 할 필요가 있다. 최적화를 위한 알고리즘은 표현된 지도 정보와 로봇의 운행 숫자에 따라 다르게 된다.

본 논문은 점유 격자지도, 점유 확률지도, 감각 데이터, 단일 및 다중 로봇 시스템의 특성을 기초로 하는 새로운 탐사 방법을 제안한다. 제안된 방법은 로봇의 탐색을 경험적으로 안내하여 단일 로봇 및 다중 로봇이 임의의 방향으로 이동하며 실험을 하였다. 확률론적인 탐색 알고리즘을 구현하기 위해 메타휴리스틱 최적화 알고리즘이 연구에 적용 되었다. 메타휴리스틱 최적화 알고리즘은 동물 행동을 수학 모델로 설명하는 알고리즘이며, 최적화 방향은 동물의 사냥, 먹이 탐색 및 진화 과정에서 모방되었다. 대표적인 최적화 알고리즘은 늑대와 고래의 사냥 방식으로 개미와 박쥐의 먹이 탐색 방법으로 수학적으로 설명 되어 있다.

본 논문은 불확실한 환경에서 모바일 로봇 탐색을 효과적으로 수행하기 위해 자연에서 영감을 얻은 Grey Wolf Optimizer, Whale Optimization, Ant Optimization Colony 그리고 Bat Optimization 알고리즘을 이용하여 다중 로봇 탐사의 최적화 기술을 적용하였다.

